

**PREVALENCE OF ZINC DEFICIENCY AND ITS ASSOCIATION WITH THE
IMMUNITY OF CHILDREN AGED 12-59 MONTHS ADMITTED ON THE
PEDIATRIC WARD OF MASAKA REGIONAL REFERRAL HOSPITAL**

By

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Declaration

I declare that the work presented in this dissertation is original and my own. It has never been carried out whether in part or full, nor presented for the award of a degree in any other University or institution.

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Approval

The research work culminating into this dissertation was conducted under my guidance and supervision.

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Dedication

To the memory of ***Mr. Robert M. Kiberu (RIP)*** and ***Mrs. Dorothy N. Kiberu (RIP)*** for their unwavering support toward this work and my life. You are my heroes, forever!

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

CBC:	Complete Blood Count
CD:	Cluster of Differentiation, Celiac Disease
CRF:	Clinical Records Form
DCs:	Dendritic Cells
DNA:	Deoxyribonucleic Acid
AE	Acrodermatitis enteropathica
EDTA:	Ethylenediamine tetraacetic Acid
ELISA:	Enzyme-Linked Immunosorbent Assay
FRC:	Faculty Research Committee
FTT	Failure-To-Thrive
HIV:	Human Immunodeficiency Virus
ICF:	International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health
IFN- γ :	Interferon-gamma
IL:	Interleukin
LBW	Low birth weight
MHC:	Major Histocompatibility Complex
mRNA:	Messenger Ribonucleic Acid
Masaka RRH:	Masaka Regional Referral Hospital
MUST:	Mbarara University of Science and Technology
MUST-REC:	Mbarara University of Science and Technology Research Ethics Committee
NF κ B:	Nuclear Factor kappa B
NK:	Natural Killer
OD:	Optical Density
PI:	Principal Investigator
PMNs:	Polymorphonuclear cells
RNA:	Ribonucleic Acid
SD:	Standard Deviations
SGA	Small-for-Gestational age
T _H :	T Helper Cell
TNF- α :	Tumor Necrosis factor alpha
UNICEF:	United Nations Children's Education Fund
ZnT:	Zinc Transporters

Definition of key terms

Adaptive immune system:	A subsystem of the immune system composed of highly specialized cells (B and T cells) and processes (production of antibodies and certain cytokines) to eliminate pathogens.
Cytokines:	Are a large group of proteins, peptides or glycoproteins that are secreted by specific cells of the immune system. They mediate and regulate immunity, inflammation and hematopoiesis.
Homeostasis:	The tendency of biological systems to maintain a relatively constant internal environment while interacting and adjusting to changes originating within or outside the system.
Immune system:	This is a host defense system consisting of structures and processes within an organism that protects against disease (detecting pathogens and distinguish them from the organism's own healthy tissue).
Immunity:	The ability of the body to resist infection or a particular disease especially from a pathogenic microorganism or by counteracting the effects of its products.
Innate immune system:	Elements of the immune system that are genetically determined, nonspecific, with fixed activities (do not change or improve as a result of exposure to antigen). They include anatomical barriers: physical barriers- intact skin and epithelia, chemical barriers- saliva, mucus, tears, lysozyme, gastric juice among others, biological barriers- normal flora; cells- neutrophils, macrophages, natural killer cells, dendritic cells, basophils, eosinophils; certain cytokines; inflammation; complement; and adhesion molecules.
Infection:	The invasion of an organism's body tissues by disease-causing agents, their multiplication, and the reaction of host tissues to the infectious agents and the toxins they produce.
Micronutrient:	A chemical element or substance required in trace amounts for the normal growth and development of living organisms for example minerals and vitamins.
Phytates:	They are antioxidants found in certain foods and vegetables. They bind dietary minerals like zinc, calcium, and iron and reduce their absorption in the gastrointestinal tract.

Zinc deficiency: Low serum zinc levels below the normal range.

Zinc supplementation: Provision of either extract from food sources or synthetic zinc to increase the intake (consumption) of the element.

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Abstract

Background: Zinc is an essential micronutrient with a variety of physiological functions. Zinc deficiency (ZnD) affects development of acquired immunity and contributes to failure to grow in children under 5. Still, there is paucity of data on the zinc status of children under 5 years of age in Uganda, particularly in hospital settings. Serum zinc status, and the association between serum zinc levels and the immune system in children aged 12 to 59 months were assessed.

Methods: This cross-sectional, laboratory-based study enrolled 40 children as they were admitted to the paediatric ward of Masaka RRH. Anthropometric measurements were taken and interpreted according to WHO growth standards charts appropriate for age and sex. Serum zinc, albumin and C-reactive protein were determined by flame absorption spectrophotometry and photometric methods respectively. Whole blood cell count was measured using an automated haemalyser, and interleukin-2 and -4 levels enzyme-linked immunosorbent assays. Student's t, Mann Whitney tests and correlation coefficients were used to determine relationships between variables.

Results: The mean age of the children was 27.8 (SD 10.6) months and females were older than males ($P < 0.003$). Nearly, a third (13/40) were undernourished, 22.5% stunted 20% wasted, and 82.5 % were anemic (Hb < 11.0 g/dL). The prevalence of ZnD was 40.6%. Serum zinc levels were positively correlated with total white blood cell ($r_s = 0.41$, $P = 0.02$) and lymphocyte ($r_s = 0.43$, $P = 0.01$) counts. Overall, children had high levels of IL-2 and IL-4, but both were not associated with ZnD.

Conclusion: The high prevalence of ZnD associated with low lymphocyte count among the under 5 children admitted to the paediatric ward of Masaka RRH is suggestive of a bigger problem in the community. Regular assessment especially of children aged below 24 months for possible zinc deficiency should be done, and zinc supplemented as an intervention, where there is high suspicion of the ZnD not only for those suffering from diarrhea.

CHAPTER 1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Zinc is an essential element (Wong and Ho, 2012, Gammoh and Rink, 2017, Wani et al., 2017, Bafaro et al., 2017) for all organisms, and the second most abundant trace metal, after iron, in the human body (Gammoh and Rink, 2017, Bitarakwate et al., 2003). Zinc is required for many cellular processes, most importantly in the processes of normal development and function of the immune system (Wong and Ho, 2012) both adaptive and innate immunity. Its significance in immune system function was established many years by Prasad in 1960s (Mocchegiani et al., 2006, Maares and Haase, 2016, Prasad, 1995).

Zinc is required for activation, development and maturation of immune cells and its deficiency affects immune cells; altering host defense, increased inflammation, and may be fatal to cause death (Maares and Haase, 2016). These include monocytes, polymorphonuclear cells, natural killer cells, T and B cells. On the contrary, excess zinc is likely to be toxic downregulating immune cell function at high levels making identification of individuals who need zinc supplementation sometimes debatable (Andree et al., 2004, Wani et al., 2017, Gammoh and Rink, 2017).

Zinc deficiency is associated with a global decrease in immune cells of both innate and adaptive immunity. It is reported that T helper (T_H) cells functions, their cytokines and the balance between the different T_H cells are affected the most (Maares and Haase, 2016, Maywald et al., 2017). The cytokine production of T_H1 cells is greatly reduced leading to an imbalance between T_H1 and T_H2 cells (Dardenne, 2002). T_H1 cytokines include IL-2, IFN- γ and TNF- α , whereas cytokines produced by T_H2 cells are IL-4, IL-6 and IL-10). During chronic deficiency, the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines increases, influencing the outcome of a large number of inflammatory diseases (Bonaventura et al., 2015).

Several other micronutrients play a vital role in maintaining a functional immune system such as vitamin D, vitamin A, vitamin B complex, vitamin C and copper. These nutrients have

immunomodulatory functions (gene expression and cellular proliferation) and thus they influence not only the host's ability to fight diarrhoeal and respiratory infections but also the course and outcome of these diseases (Bhaskaram, 2002).

Zinc deficiency is related to nutrition inadequacy or malabsorption of dietary zinc. Intake varies from absorption due to high phytates and fiber in the diet, which consequently reduces absorption. Losses have also been reported in children and adults with diarrhea. It is estimated that zinc deficiency affects about one-third of the world's population with wide variations in estimates ranging from 4% to 73% across sub-regions. In 2002, WHO reported that zinc deficiency was associated with nearly 16% of lower respiratory tract infections, 18% of malaria and 10% of diarrhoeal diseases worldwide (World Health Organization, 2002). Unfortunately, there is hardly any data on the current situation especially in the third world countries including Uganda, where such diseases are highly prevalent making the proposed study relevant.

Zinc deficiency is among the common deficiencies associated with undernutrition, and an important cause of morbidity and mortality among young children in developing countries where zinc intake is inadequate (de Benoist et al., 2007, King et al., 2015). Worldwide, 202 million children under 5 years of age are undernourished with more than a third in Africa (United Nations Children's Fund/World Health Organization/World Bank Group, 2018). Nearly, a similar trend observed in Uganda where nearly 1 in every 5 children is stunted (UBOS and ICF, 2017, USAID, 2018).

The southwestern part of Uganda is among the regions with the highest prevalence of malnutrition for the under 5-year old despite the region being referred to as the "food basket" of Uganda (USAID, 2018, Kikafunda et al., 2014). A previous study reported that almost half (47.8%) of the children below 5 years in western Uganda were stunted (Kikafunda et al., 2014). Moreover, undernutrition is common among children between 6 months to 5 years (WHO,

2013) as well as zinc deficiency in low- and middle-income countries (Abd El-Ghaffar et al., 2022).

Given the high proportion of undernutrition within this age bracket, this study aimed at, firstly, establishing the prevalence of zinc deficiency among children aged 12 and 59 months. Secondly, to assess the effect of low zinc levels on white blood cells (WBC) including total WBC, neutrophil, lymphocyte, monocyte, eosinophil and basophil counts, and interleukins 2 and 4 levels among children aged 12 to 59 months. Assessment of white blood cell numbers in general represented the innate immunity and assessment of interleukins 2 and 4 represented the adaptive immunity arm.

1.2 Problem statement

Zinc deficiency is the third most common micronutrient deficiency after iron and vitamin A among children under-5 (Imdad and Bhutta, 2012). Together, they are responsible for nearly half of the deaths in the under-five children worldwide (World Health Organisation, 2013). According to the Uganda Nutrition Action Plan 2011-2016, the prevalence of zinc deficiency ranged from 20 to 70% in young children (Government of Uganda, 2017). Zinc deficiency places children in many low-income countries including Uganda at increased risk of illness and death from preventable infectious diseases.

Evidence from clinical trials of zinc supplementation demonstrated benefits of a prevention approach. Pooled analyses of clinical trials demonstrated that groups that received zinc had 18% reduction of diarrhea, 41% lower rate of pneumonia, and 68% reduction in mortality in small-for-gestational-age (SGA) term infants who were given zinc supplements from 1 to 9 months of age (Black, 2003).

In Masaka RRH zinc is supplemented during the management of diarrhea. In Uganda, currently 10 and 20 mg of zinc is supplemented daily for up to two weeks during the management of diarrhea and routine standard care of healthy children does not include zinc supplementation (Datta et al., 2019).

In a previous study, preventive zinc supplementation was seen to outweigh associated harms like vomiting where the risk of zinc deficiency is relatively high (Mayo-Wilson et al., 2014). There are reports indicating that benefits are better when zinc is supplemented at early stages of growth retardation. Zinc supplementation is less likely to have effects on growth in the stunted children (Park et al., 2017). In southern Uganda, and the country at large, there is paucity of information concerning the prevalence of zinc deficiency and its effect in children. Given the important association between zinc deficiency and the immune system response, this study sought to provide preliminary information on the extent of zinc deficiency and the effect of low serum zinc on the immunity of children aged between 12 to 59 months.

1.3 Research questions

1. What is the prevalence of zinc deficiency in children aged 12 to 59 months admitted to the paediatrics ward of Masaka Regional Referral Hospital (Masaka RRH)?
2. Is there an association between low serum zinc levels and white blood cell counts in the children aged 12 to 59 months admitted to the paediatrics ward of Masaka RRH?
3. Is there an association between low serum zinc levels and interleukin (IL)-2 and IL-4 levels in the children aged 12 to 59 months admitted to the paediatrics ward of Masaka RRH?

1.4 Objectives

1.4.1 General objective

To determine the prevalence of zinc deficiency and assess the association between low serum zinc levels and the immune system in children aged 12 to 59 months admitted to the paediatrics ward of Masaka RRH.

1.4.2 Specific objectives

1. To determine the prevalence of zinc deficiency in children aged 12 to 59 months admitted at Masaka RRH.
2. To determine the association between low serum zinc levels and white blood cell counts of the children aged 12 to 59 months admitted at Masaka RRH.

3. To establish the association between zinc status and interleukin (IL)-2 and IL-4 levels in children aged 12 to 59 months admitted at Masaka RRH.

1.5 Significance of the study

Despite evidence from studies reporting an improvement in outcomes during zinc supplementation, outside research, it has not been widely taken up in clinical settings in particular as a preventive measure yet zinc deficiency is not uncommon. Previous studies demonstrated that zinc supplementation lowers infection rates (Gammoh and Rink, 2017), reduces case fatality in severe childhood pneumonia (Wang and Song, 2018, Acevedo-Murillo et al., 2019) and illnesses related to diarrhea among children supplemented with zinc (Barffour et al., 2020). Furthermore, zinc supplementation is one of the essential elements recommended for use in the management of diarrhea in children (World Health Organization, 2013). Moreover, when a population has more than 20% of its individuals with a lower serum zinc below cutoff accounting for age and sex, the risk of zinc deficiency should be considered an issue of public health importance (Alves et al., 2016).

The findings from the current study reveal a high prevalence (40.6%) of zinc deficiency among children under-five among children admitted at Masaka RRH. The study demonstrates that use of height-for-age (stunting) to determine the prevalence of zinc provides an underestimate given that the current study's prevalence based on the latter was 22.5%. The study also provides evidence of the deranged immune responses among children admitted at Masaka RRH as a result of zinc deficiency with a significant lymphopenia alongside reduced total white blood cell, neutrophil and basophil count.

The study findings may form a basis for larger and comprehensive studies in children under-5 regarding the prevalence of zinc deficiency and its effects in hospital settings. Recent evidence shows that the emphasized dietary changes alone do not correct zinc levels among children (Ahsan et al., 2021). Therefore, the findings from the current study might guide policy formulation to initiate zinc supplementation among children under 5 who are at risk of or have

zinc deficiency in Masaka RRH and similar settings in Uganda. This study has identified a zinc-related deranged immune response and stunting among children and suggests an approach that could contribute to achieving target 2 of Goal 3 of the Sustainable Development Goals, which emphasizes ending preventable deaths of newborns and children under 5 years of age.

1.6 Conceptual framework

Key: —————> Effect. Adapted from Katona and Katona-Apte, 2008 with modifications.

Figure 1. Factors associated with zinc deficiency and its effect on the immune system. Low serum zinc levels, herein referred to as zinc deficiency, majorly result from inadequate intake, and/or consumption of foodstuffs high in fiber and phytate (Figure 1). The latter inhibits optimal absorption of zinc. Diarrhoea causes mucosal injury and when persistent, it leads to both reduced absorption of nutrients (zinc inclusive) and endogenous loss of zinc in stools (Afolabi et al., 2018). Damaged gut mucosa means the natural barrier to entry of pathogens is compromised and infections may ensue. Zinc deficiency affects normal development and function of both innate (neutrophils, macrophages, natural killer cells) and adaptive immunity (lymphocytes, Th1 cytokine release and antibody production- IgG in particular) (Wessels et al., 2017). The affected individual becomes more susceptible to infections.

CHAPTER 2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Overview

This chapter provides a synthesis of literature on the role of zinc in growth, the immune system, the mechanisms of zinc homeostasis and its disturbance in a vulnerable population, namely children under five years. Zinc is an essential micronutrient element for all life forms (Xia et al., 2021). Zinc is present in foods (like meats, poultry, beans, nuts, and others), may be added to others or given as a supplement. It is also found in over-the-counter drugs, sold as remedies for cold (Office of Dietary Supplements NIH, 2018). Zinc has many roles in cellular activities including catalytic activities of many enzymes (more than 300 hundred) (Prasad, 2014a), has a role in immune function, protein synthesis (Elmadfa and Meyer, 2019), smell and taste and is essential for cellular proliferation (Singh and Dubey, 2019) In other words, it plays a role in growth and development. To maintain normal levels, daily intake is highly recommended as the body lacks zinc stores (Rink, 2000, Maxfield et al., 2021).

Inadequate intake and or increased losses like persistent diarrhoea are the major causes of zinc deficiency. In children who have rapid growth, zinc deficiency results in failure to thrive (stunting). Clinical zinc deficiency mainly affects the gastrointestinal, immune, central nervous, skeletal, and reproductive systems (Roohani et al., 2013). Low-income areas which highly feed on diets high cereal and low animal diets have higher prevalence of zinc deficiency (Abd El-Ghaffar et al., 2022)

Unfortunately, previous studies have reported inadequate zinc levels in most traditional foods in Uganda (Tidemann-Andersen et al., 2011, Kikafunda et al., 1998). Currently, nearly a third of children under 5 are stunted (USAID, 2018). Whereas the National Food and Nutrition Policy of Uganda deliberates among other things to eliminate nutritional disorders, the focus on micronutrients is toward iodine, vitamin A and iron, with lesser focus on zinc in Uganda. Moreover, there is no clear available statistics on the national prevalence of zinc deficiency (Tidemann-Andersen et al., 2011) or guidelines of its prevention in routine care. This implies that less is known about the effects of zinc, not only among children, but also adults in Uganda;

studies are needed for proper planning and implementation. Given that the emphasized dietary modification alone has been reported to be insufficient to correct zinc deficiency (Ahsan et al., 2021), health facilities are of interest given their capability to conduct comprehensive assessment and offer interventions, especially in acute zinc deficiency, for the most vulnerable groups –children under 5.

2.2 Role of zinc in growth

Zinc is vital for cellular growth, cellular metabolism, and differentiation. Deficiency has been linked to reduced children's growth (Ahsan et al., 2021). Zinc plays a wide variety of cellular processes as a cofactor for many enzymes and influences gene expression (Banupriya et al., 2020). Zinc is linked to deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA), ribonucleic acid (RNA) and protein synthesis. In these processes, zinc is tightly bound to the enzymes facilitating their actions (Thompson, 2022). In addition, zinc enhances the function of the growth hormone and insulin-like growth factor 1. The latter is important in the induction of cell proliferation and differentiation of chondrocytes, osteoblasts, and fibroblasts (Inzaghi et al., 2022) all of which are important for linear growth.

Zinc improves linear growth of children under the age of five (World Health Organisation, 2018). Furthermore, it is known to have effects on mechanisms of smell, taste, appetite and thus food consumption (Brandão-Neto et al., 1995, MacDonald, 2000). Some studies, however, have shown no overall effect of zinc supplementation on the growth of children (Bates et al., 1993, Salmenperä et al., 1994, Kikafunda et al., 1998).

In addition, the under 5 are the most affected with conditions associated with zinc deficiency including malaria, pneumonia and diarrhoea. These infections, due to zinc deficiency become recurrent and negatively affect their growth (Abd El-Ghaffar et al., 2022).

2.3 Zinc and the immune system

Zinc is an essential trace element for the functioning of the immune system. It has both innate and adaptive multifaceted influences on the immune function (Wessels et al., 2017). The

effects of zinc on immunity are rooted in its numerous roles in basic cellular functions such as DNA replication, RNA transcription, cell division, cell activation and apoptosis (Lambert et al., 2018, Wessels et al., 2017, Maret, 2019)

Zinc deficiency is associated with increased susceptibility to a variety of infections like pneumonia, shigellosis, malaria, and tuberculosis (Gammoh and Rink, 2017, Maywald et al., 2017). The impaired functions are reversed upon zinc supplementation (Li et al., 2022). The consequences of zinc deficiency in humans include thymic atrophy, altered thymic hormones, reduced number of lymphocytes, and compromised cellular and antibody-mediated responses resulting in increased rates and duration of infection (Skrajnowska and Bobrowska-Korczak, 2019).

These general findings suggest that zinc is critical for normal immune cell function and that zinc depletion causes immune cell dysfunction. Zinc supplementation either restores function in the setting of dysfunction or improve normal immune cell function (Gammoh and Rink, 2017). In addition, negative effects have been reported with high doses of zinc, similar to those during zinc deficiency (Maywald et al., 2017).

2.3.1 Innate, non-specific immunity

Innate immunity initiates an immediate immune response upon recognition of pathogens. This includes the natural killer (NK) cells, dendritic cells (DCs), macrophages, mast cells, granulocytes, and complement components (Maares and Haase, 2016). Zinc is important in maintaining the physical barriers including skin, gastrointestinal and pulmonary tracts another component of innate immunity (Shankar and Prasad, 1998, Wessels et al., 2020).

Zinc influences chemotaxis and phagocytosis in polymorphonuclear cells, regulates oxidative burst (superoxide anion production) responsible for the destruction of pathogens (Maares and Haase, 2016) via its antioxidant actions (Prasad, 2009).

Zinc promotes adhesion of monocytes to endothelial cells, production of cytokines interleukin-6 (IL-6) and tumor necrosis factor α (TNF- α) by monocytes (, and promotes maturation of dendritic cells by upregulating expression of surface receptors – major histocompatibility complex II (MHC-II) (Bonaventura et al., 2015). Natural killer (NK) cells recognize and kill tumor and virus-infected cells (Vivier et al., 2011) through two zinc-dependent mechanisms that increase expression of perforins and an IL-2-enhanced NK cytotoxicity (Rolles et al., 2018). During zinc deficiency, the above actions are defective, leading to infections like pneumonia and illnesses like diarrhea being severe and recurrent.

2.3.2 Adaptive immunity

The adaptive immune response is based on two groups of lymphocytes, B and T cells. B cells differentiate into immunoglobulin-secreting plasma cells thereby inducing humoral immunity. T cells mediate cytotoxic and helper cell functions of cell-mediated immunity (McComb et al., 2019).

Lymphocytes express specific receptors on their surface to detect antigens. After antigen recognition, the lymphocytes selectively proliferate and become activated into T and B cell clones leading to a highly antigen-specific cellular immune response. Altered zinc homeostasis influences lymphocyte function and development by directly affecting their formation (lymphopoiesis) and cytokine production or indirectly due to impaired stimulation by innate immune cells (Skrajnowska and Bobrowska-Korczak, 2019)

T cells are divided into the cytotoxic CD₈⁺ T cells and CD₄⁺ T helper (T_H) cells (McComb et al., 2019). The former recognize and eliminate virally infected and tumor cells. The latter promote functions of other immune cells, that is, activating infected monocytes to kill phagocytosed pathogens (T_H1 cells) or supporting antibody production by B cells (T_H2 cells) via cytokine production (Haase and Rink, 2014).

T cells are the most vulnerable to zinc deficiency states including their development and functioning (Skrajnowska and Bobrowska-Korczak, 2019). Given that maturation of T cells occurs in the thymus gland, zinc deficiency is known to cause thymic atrophy and T cell lymphopenia. There is a reduction in maturation and increased apoptosis of pre-T cells is observed in zinc deficiency (Weyh et al., 2022).

In addition, T cell function is affected by thymulin activity during zinc deficiency. Thymulin, a peptide produced by thymic epithelial cells requires zinc to promote T cell maturation, cytotoxicity and IL-2 production (Zhang et al., 2015). Zinc is also required for the IL-2 dependent proliferation of activated T cells (Kim and Lee, 2021).

Decreased proliferation and differentiation observed in zinc deficiency affect the function and balance of T_H cell types majorly T_{H1} and T_{H2} subtypes whose balance is crucial for effective immune response (Maares and Haase, 2016). T_{H1} cytokines (IL-2, INF- γ and TNF- α) are reduced by zinc deficiency (Gruber et al., 2013, Maywald et al., 2017). IFN- γ mainly stimulates T_{H1} development, macrophages, dendritic cells (Bao et al., 2011, Ivashkiv, 2018) and attenuates T_{H2} (Ivashkiv, 2018).

IL-2 is produced by activated T cells mainly T_{H1} cells, but also by activated CD8⁺ T cells, NK cells, dendritic cells and macrophages (Liao et al., 2011, Mitra and Leonard, 2018). IL-2 has key roles in the immune system: tolerance and immunity via direct effects on T cells.

In the thymus, IL-2 promotes differentiation of immature T cells into T_{H1} and T_{H2} cells and suppresses T cells which would otherwise attack normal body ("self") cells (Arenas-Ramirez et al., 2015). IL-2 is also known to induce activation-induced cell death as a result of repeated T cell receptor activation (Arenas-Ramirez et al., 2015, Riou et al., 2006), promotes differentiation and proliferation of antigen-activated T cells into effector and memory cells (Mitra and Leonard, 2018). In this study, IL-2 was used as a biomarker for normal T_H cell

differentiation and normal T_H1 cell function. The study sought to identify the effect of serum zinc levels on IL-2 in young children.

On the other hand, IL-4 is produced majorly by T_H2, mast cells and basophils (Brown and Hural, 2017). The initial source of IL-4 is unknown, but there are reports suggesting that basophils may be involved (Ma and Gao, 2020). After basophils have been directly activated by allergens, they produce T_H2 inducing cytokines such as IL-4. IL-4 induces differentiation of naïve T helper cells into T_H2 cells which subsequently produce additional IL-4 in positive feedback (Kasal et al., 2021).

IL-4 is vital in supporting the growth and differentiation of B cells into antibody-producing cells (Junttila, 2018). It is known to regulate a myriad of immune functions including immunoglobulin (Ig) isotype switching to IgE, class II MHC expression by B cells (Brown and Hural, 2017) and prevents cell death of naïve B cells and Tregs (Yang et al., 2017). Thus, this study sought to describe the effect of serum zinc levels on IL-4 in young children. IL-4 was used as a biomarker of normal growth and differentiation of B cells, which in the presence of microorganisms would be activated to produce antibodies.

Whereas T_H1 cytokine production is reduced in zinc deficiency, T_H2 cytokines (IL-4, IL-6 and IL-10) are less affected resulting into an imbalance between T_H1 and T_H2 subsets with a net shift toward T_H2 (Prasad, 2000, Kido et al., 2019). Several studies have investigated the relationship between T_H1 cells and zinc concentration (Acevedo-Murillo et al., 2019, Dünkelberg et al., 2020, Kahmann et al., 2006). Low zinc levels have been reported to upregulate messenger ribonucleic acid (mRNA) levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines via the nuclear factor κB (NFκB) pathway (Jarosz et al., 2017).

2.4 Zinc homeostasis

It is well known that maintaining a constant state of cellular homeostasis is essential for the normal function of cells. In humans, this is achieved by dietary intake, adjustments in zinc absorption and zinc excretion by intestines. Furthermore, cellular redistribution of zinc plays a

role in the maintenance of zinc homeostasis (King et al., 2000). The kidneys play a lesser role particularly in situations of increased intake (Kambe et al., 2015).

2.4.1 Zinc distribution in the body

The normal serum zinc reference ranges are 64–124 µg/dL with no age or sex dependence in children 0.5-18 years from a healthy Caucasian population, (Lin et al., 2012). Earlier, Farhan et al. (1969) reported a range of 60-100 ug/dL, which is in agreement with what was reported by Krebs (2013). Currently, there is no available information of locally established zinc reference values in Ugandan setting. So, this study used 57-160 ug/dL for non-fasting children under 10 years (International Zinc Nutrition Consultative Group, 2020).

As a trace element, zinc forms less than 0.01% of the body weight with the highest concentration in hair, eyes, bones and male organs (Walravens, 1979) and total human body amounting to 2-4 g (Gammoh and Rink, 2017). Zinc is found in the biologic state complexed to organic ligands such as metalloenzymes, with little free in solution as a metallic ion. Nearly 50% of plasma zinc is bound loosely to albumin and is freely exchangeable.

Approximately 7% is bound to amino acids, and the remainder is bound to macroglobulins and other serum proteins (Gordon et al., 1981, Walravens, 1979). Lack of a specialized storage system in the body means a daily intake of zinc is required to achieve a steady-state (Rink, 2000, Gammoh and Rink, 2017).

A wide range of foods contains zinc, with poultry and meat foods having the highest concentration. However, in resource-limited settings like Uganda, the population mainly feeds on plant-based diets like beans, cereals, legumes and vegetables which have moderate amounts. In addition, this diet contains a high phytate content which binds and inhibits absorption of zinc (Neufingerl and Eilander, 2021). As such a predominantly vegetarian diet is expected to be an important predisposing factor for zinc deficiency.

Malabsorption, persistent diarrhea, and rare genetic disorders such as acrodermatitis enteropathica lead to a non-diet zinc deficiency which even with normal intake, absorption is reduced (Hassan et al., 2020). Diarrhoea is associated with poor absorption because of reduced transit time and destruction of the gut mucosa. When secretory, diarrhea greatly reduces net absorption.

Diarrhoea is a serious cause of morbidity and mortality in children under 5 worldwide. In low- and middle-income countries, it is a leading cause of illness and deaths in the same age group (Mokomane et al., 2018). More than two-thirds of these deaths occur in Africa and South-East Asia (Yeshaw et al., 2020).

Zinc homeostasis is maintained majorly by two processes, that is, absorption from and secretion into the gastrointestinal tract. The kidneys and the bones have less contribution under normal physiological states (Krebs, 2013). Absorption is 16-50% of the amount ingested and inversely related to oral zinc concentration (Maares and Haase, 2020). This means that absorption depends on the concentration of zinc in the diet.

Rink suggested that daily intake should be adjusted according to one's health status (Rink, 2000) and bodily physiological need requirements. As such, infants, pregnant and lactating mothers, and individuals with chronic low zinc intakes or diets with poor bioavailability (Krebs, 2000) are at risk. Conversely, there are reports that zinc status of an individual does not determine the efficiency of zinc absorption (King, 2010).

Zinc is absorbed mainly in the duodenum and proximal small intestine. The process requires energy in the form of adenosine triphosphate (ATP) via zinc transporter, ZIP4. The receptors are found across the apical membrane of the enterocytes (Cousins, 2010). Secretion of endogenous zinc into the gastrointestinal tract is facilitated by another group of receptors, ZnT. Different receptor types (both ZIP and ZnT) exist on the surfaces of many cells like

immune cells and pancreatic acinar cells to perform similar functions of maintaining 'normal' zinc metabolism (Sekler et al., 2007, Cousins, 2010).

The main carrier of zinc in circulation is serum albumin. Infections alter zinc distribution by markedly reducing plasma levels. A small pool of free zinc remains within plasma and the rest (nearly 99.9%) inside cells, to avoid its access by pathogens. This is a protective measure the body undertakes to fight pathogens, a part of natural immunity (Gammoh and Rink, 2017). This reduces the free bioavailable zinc ions. The reduction is great if there's an existing zinc deficiency. Therefore, in limited settings where infections are frequent, zinc deficiency is more prevalent.

2.4.2 Disturbances of zinc homeostasis in children

Impaired zinc homeostasis is highly implicated for zinc deficiency. In children, zinc deficiency hinders normal growth resulting in stunting and low weight, and hampers intellectual development (Chasapis et al., 2012). Children with zinc deficiency have thin sparse hair (alopecia), erythema and rough skin with poor and delayed wound healing. Other clinical manifestations include recurrent infections, diarrhoea, poor appetite, poor taste and delay to attain puberty (Prasad, 2020, Roohani et al., 2013).

Low dietary intake poses a risk to exclusively breastfed older infants. It was observed that there is a sharp and then a progressive decrease of zinc content in human milk from above 3 mg/L at the start to less than 1 mg/L by 6 months (Krebs, 2013). An increased volume of breast milk, however, does not compensate for the decline of zinc content in breast milk. In fact, by about 6 months of age, the breastfed infant becomes more dependent on other sources to meet the physiologic needs (Krebs and Hambidge, 2007).

As such, toddlers on mixed diets are at risk of inadequate intake if complementary feeds lack significant bioavailable zinc, for example, unfortified infant cereals (Krebs, 2013) which are staple foods in low- and middle-income countries. Therefore, children from such settings are at a risk of zinc deficiency early in life and complementary feeds might not meet their needs.

Impaired absorption is observed in clinical conditions including acrodermatitis enteropathica (AE), celiac disease (CD), cystic fibrosis (CF), liver disease and short bowel syndrome. AE is a genetic and severe form of zinc deficiency which results from a partial block in intestinal zinc absorption due to mutations in ZIP gene. ZIP gene codes for metal ion transporter of zinc on the surface of cells (Wang et al., 2002). The disease presents after weaning with three essential symptoms: cutaneous manifestations: periorificial dermatitis and alopecia and diarrhoea, being the most extracutaneous manifestation (Nistor et al., 2016, Van Wouwe, 1989). These three symptoms, in combination, are found only in 20% of the patients (Van Wouwe, 1989).

AE presents with severe zinc deficiency signs and symptoms: failure to thrive, impaired immunity, poor appetite, gastrointestinal symptoms, weight loss or failure to gain weight, frequent infections, emotional lability, and neurological disorders (Maverakis et al., 2007).

Celiac disease is an immune-mediated disorder triggered by dietary gluten. Both impaired zinc absorption and increased endogenous fecal losses of zinc have been reported (Tran et al., 2011). The disease predominantly affects the proximal small intestine, a region wherein healthy people, absorption of zinc is most efficient (Scrimgeour and Condlin, 2009). In a study to determine the serum zinc levels in children with celiac disease, 23 out of 30 (approximately 77%) had significantly lower levels of zinc. In addition, most of the children with low levels were newly diagnosed and severely malnourished.

Cystic fibrosis (CF) is an autosomal recessive disease resulting from mutations in the gene that codes for cyclic adenosine monophosphate-activated chloride channel, the CF transmembrane protein (Abdulhamid et al., 2008). The disease affects several organs, predominantly the respiratory and gastrointestinal tracts. Pancreatic insufficiency characterized by the disease may result in malabsorption of various nutrients including zinc,

essential fatty acids and fat-soluble vitamins (Easley et al., 1998). In addition, there are intestinal mucosal abnormalities associated with CF that cause diarrhoea (Krebs et al., 1998).

There are inconsistencies in the study findings regarding zinc status and CF. Krebs et al. (1998) reported a 30% prevalence of low serum zinc levels in young infants with CF. A lower prevalence of 10% with no association to nutritional status was reported by Akanli et al. (2003). Plasma zinc levels were lower in patients with moderate-to-severe growth retardation and with moderate CF disease (Neve et al., 1983), in contrast to the findings that suggested that zinc was not a limiting factor in children with CF and mild-to-moderate lung disease (Maqbool et al., 2006).

Short bowel syndrome (SBS) is a malabsorptive disease that occurs as a result of surgical resection (acquired) or congenital disease of a significant short proportion of the small intestine (Duro et al., 2008b, Carey et al., 2016). Children with SBS are at risk of macro- and micronutrient deficiencies including zinc, as a result of reduced surface area for absorption (Duro et al., 2008a) and malabsorptive diarrhoea (Duro et al., 2008b). In a case report of a 3-year-old girl with acquired (surgical during neonatal period) SBS due to gastroschisis, bowel dilatation and ileal atresia, her laboratory evaluation revealed micronutrient deficiencies (vitamin A, D, E, K and zinc (50µl/dL) at 3 years (Duro et al., 2008a).

In liver disease, causes of zinc deficiency are multifactorial. There is an induction of hepatic metallothionein that binds and sequesters zinc in the liver. Other factors are anorexia (causing a reduced dietary intake) and alteration in intestinal transport (Krebs, 2013). Zinc deficiency occurs in many types of liver disease, more so in the advanced disease. Some proposed mechanisms responsible for the altered zinc metabolism include decreased dietary intake, increased urinary excretion and activation of certain zinc transporters (Mohammad et al., 2012). The decrease in albumin synthesis, increase in α 2-macroglobulin which strongly binds

zinc, and impaired intestinal absorption of zinc in liver cirrhosis, all, result in severe zinc deficiency (Himoto and Masaki, 2018).

Evidence from studies has shown that there is an improvement with zinc supplementation in the above conditions. Complete resolution of symptoms has been reported where the inadequate intake was responsible as well as in cases of AE (Krebs, 2013). Improvement in levels of albumin, daily calorie intake, weight and forced expiratory volume and reduced infections in patients with cystic fibrosis were reported in a study about the effect of zinc supplements in CF on disease evolution (Van Biervliet et al., 2008). This study did not focus on ascertaining the possible causes of zinc deficiency among study participants.

2.5 Prevalence of zinc deficiency

Zinc deficiency is endemic in up to one-third of the population in various parts of the world, majorly in sub-Saharan Africa (Hess, 2017) and that growth retardation commonly observed in these countries may indeed be due to zinc deficiency (Goudet et al., 2019).

Up to 17.3% of the world's population by 2012 was at risk of inadequate zinc intake, mostly in the developing world such as Sub-Saharan Africa where it was above 25% and thus a higher risk of zinc deficiency (Wessells and Brown, 2012). A growth-limiting, mild zinc deficiency syndrome was identified in developed countries in medium-to-low income families (Kikafunda et al., 1998).

A study conducted in South Africa about the prevalence of iron and zinc deficiency among rural preschool going children (3 to 5 years old) found out that 42.6% of the participants were zinc-deficient and 16.8% were stunted (Motadi et al., 2015). These values may be comparable to the Uganda situation where 1 in 5 (20%) children under 5 years are stunted (UBOS and ICF, 2017). Prevalence of zinc deficiency in Uganda is given as a range of 20 to 70% (Government of Uganda, 2017).

The risk of zinc deficiency is considered to be elevated if the prevalence of inadequate intake is greater than 25% (de Benoist et al., 2007). As such, study sought to determine the prevalence of zinc deficiency in children under-5 admitted in a regional referral hospital.

2.6 Assessment of zinc status

Use of plasma or serum is popular, and remains the best biomarker, but an imperfect biomarker of zinc status (Krebs, 2013). The rationale for this is that serum or plasma reflects dietary zinc intake and responds consistently to zinc supplementation (de Benoist et al., 2007, Mayo-Wilson et al., 2014, Park et al., 2017).

Other recommended indicators are dietary and functional. For dietary indicators, the prevalence or proportion of zinc intakes below the appropriate estimated average requirement are used, as determined from quantitative dietary intake. With existing evidence indicating that stunted children respond to zinc supplementation, height-for-age is considered to be the functional indicator of zinc deficiency (Gibson et al., 2008, Wieringa et al., 2015).

If the prevalence of low height-for-age is or more than 20%, the prevalence of zinc deficiency may be elevated. All the three indicators, when used together, provide the best estimate of the risk of zinc deficiency in a population, be used to identify specific subgroups with higher risk, and indicate the need for zinc supplementation (de Benoist et al., 2007).

The current study exploited the assessment tools including serum zinc levels, and height-for-age scores to determine the prevalence and/or the risk of zinc deficiency. It is worth noting that assessment of the risk of zinc deficiency in the clinical setting relies on a good history; including diet and feeding history, and a review of systems addressing potential gastrointestinal pathology (Krebs et al., 2014). This study aimed at determining the prevalence of zinc deficiency and its effect on the immune system of the children admitted at Masaka RRH Paediatric ward using the biochemical parameter (serum zinc levels), clinical presentations of zinc deficiency: nutritional status- height and weight-for-age score and/or stigmata for zinc deficiency.

Zinc is negatively affected by acute-phase reactants and thus its concentration may decrease in the presence of inflammation. The acute response can lead to a redistribution from the plasma to the liver, which could lead to elevated estimates of the prevalence of zinc deficiency, in a setting of high infection. As such, adjustments of serum zinc concentrations for inflammation using inflammatory markers such as c-reactive protein (CRP) are required when assessing and providing estimates for zinc deficiency in a population (McDonald et al., 2020, Karakochuk et al., 2017). In this study, we adjusted serum zinc concentrations for CRP to provide estimates for zinc deficiency in the study population.

CHAPTER 3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Study design

This was a cross-sectional, laboratory-based study to determine the prevalence and effect of low serum zinc levels among children aged between 12 and 59 months admitted to the Paediatric ward of Masaka Regional Referral Hospital.

3.2 Study setting

The study was conducted at the Pediatrics admission unit of Masaka RRH. The Hospital is located in Masaka City, Masaka District about 132 km southwest of Uganda's capital city Kampala. Masaka Regional Referral Hospital was founded in 1927 and elevated to regional referral status in 1996 (Uganda Ministry of Health, 2019). It provides referral services for the Southern Central districts of Masaka, Rakai, Lyantonde, Lwengo, Ssembabule, Bukomansimbi, Kalungu and Kalagala. It has a bed capacity of 330 beds and admits about 24,000 patients annually. Masaka Regional Referral hospital offers surgical, medical, obstetrics and gynaecology, paediatrics, diagnostics, and pharmaceutical services as well as nutritional support for both children and adults. The Paediatrics ward of Masaka RRH has about 40 beds on the general ward, 8 beds in the nutritional unit and one isolation unit with 2 beds. On average, the ward admits between 80-120 sick children, with several seasonal variations. Of these, 45 are aged between 12 and 59 months. The ward has 3 doctors (2 paediatricians and one medical officer) and 7 nurses. The health facility offers training to undergraduate medical students.

The health facility offers training to undergraduate medical students. The paediatrics ward of MRRH has about 40 beds on general ward and nutritional unit of 6 beds with 3 doctors (2 paediatricians and one medical officer) and 7 nurses.

Masaka RRH has two laboratory facilities; the general laboratory and private-wing laboratory. Both laboratories have the capacity to carry out routine clinical haematological (full blood counts), serological (serum albumin, electrolytes among others), microbial (cultures and sensitivity) and other diagnostic tests. The facilities do not provide advanced immunological

tests like cytokine profiles. At times, the Masaka RRH laboratory facilities are not fully functional, and nearby private laboratory facilities provide the services.

3.3 Study population.

The target population was children under five years of age; specifically, children aged 12 months to 59 months admitted to the Paediatric ward of Masaka RRH between December 2021 and January 2022.

3.4 Sample size and sampling criteria

3.4.1 Sample size estimation

The sample size was estimated using statistical table for determining sample size for a finite population (Krejcie and Morgan, 1970). The Masaka RRH Paediatrics Ward admits on average 45 children between the age of 12 to 59 months in a month. At 95% confidence interval, $Z_{\alpha/2}$ (1.96), margin of error = 0.05, the estimated sample size is 40 children.

$$n = \frac{X^2 N p q}{(ME^2 (N - 1)) + (X^2 p q)} ; n = \frac{3.8421^2 * 45 * 0.5 * 0.5}{(0.05^2 * (45 - 1)) + (3.841^2 * 0.5 * 0.5)}$$

; $n \approx 40$ n = sample size, X^2 = Chi-square for the specified confidence level (95%) at 1 degree of freedom (3.841), N = population size (45), p = population proportion (0.5), $q = p-1$, ME = desired margin of error (0.05).

3.5 Eligibility criteria

3.5.1 Inclusion criteria

- Children of either sex aged 12 to 59 months.
- Willingness of the parent (guardian) to provide written informed consent to participate in the study.

3.5.2 Exclusion criteria

- Those who would have received zinc as treatment of diarrhoea or therapeutic feeds including F-75, F-100, diluted therapeutic milk (DTM), Ready-To-Use Therapeutic Food (RUTF) in the past 28 days.

3.4.2 Sampling procedure

Children satisfying the selection criteria (section 3.5) were recruited into the study consecutively until the calculated sample size was attained. Recruitment of participants was

done at admission by a nursing officer (research assistant) and the principal investigator (PI) who approached the caretaker prior to admission on ward. The RA was informed in detail about the study objectives, procedures (consenting, anthropometry, blood sample collection and storage) and data collection. Additionally, the RA was trained in how to administer informed consent, and storage of samples prior to analysis. Care was taken not to disrupt the admission process or routine care of the children on the ward, by 1) A little extra blood was collected by the clinical team when drawing what was needed for routine care, so phlebotomy was done once and 2) written consent was obtained after the child had received the initial treatment at the admission unit.

3.6 Data collection procedures

3.6.1 Data collection tools and study procedures.

A clinical record form was used to collect data on anthropometry and signs of zinc deficiency.

The RA identified the potential participants while the sick children were being admitted to the Paediatrics ward. The RA took anthropometry measurements, collected blood samples in the purple top (1 mL) and red (2 mL) top vacutainers.

3.6.2 Anthropometry

Anthropometric measurements (weight, height, and mid-upper arm circumference (MUAC)) of the children were taken by the research assistant following the Uganda Ministry of Health Integrated Management of Acute Malnutrition guidelines of measuring height and length (MoH Uganda, 2016) . Weight was measured using calibrated weighing scales for those who were able to stand. For children who could stand, height was recorded to the nearest 0.1 cm using a height measuring board. For infants and very young children, body length was recorded to 0.1 cm using a stadiometer. The MUAC of each child's upper arm was measured using a nonstretch insertion tape. The age of the children was calculated to the nearest month the children's birth records (child health card, CHC). Where no birth records were available, the age was estimated using major national and/or international events around the birth of the child.

3.6.3 Sample collection and handling

Blood was drawn by the trained nursing officer from either cubital or femoral vein. As much as possible, drawing blood was done together with what was required for routine clinical procedures. About 3 mL of blood were collected under aseptic measures into a free anticoagulant tube (BD Vacutainer Serum Separator Tube) for measurement of zinc serum, C-reactive protein, and enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) for IL-2 and IL-4. Another 1 mL of blood was collected into an anticoagulant-coated tube (BD Vacutainer EDTA) for complete blood count (CBC). Samples were kept on ice and then taken to the laboratory for further processing and analysis. CBC and CRP analyses were done within an hour after collection. Serum samples for the measurement of zinc, and interleukins -2 and -4 were frozen at -20^o C until analysis.

Blood samples collected from participants were analyzed (full blood count, serum albumin and serum c-reactive protein), processed and stored (at -20^oC) at The Lancet Laboratory, Masaka branch located in Katwe Masaka City. The Lancet laboratories, Uganda are accredited laboratories with capacity and capabilities to carryout high-quality diagnostics in the medical field. Serum cytokines (IL-2 and IL-4) were analyzed at Joint Clinical Research Center (JCRC) Laboratory, located Lubowa, Kampala. JCRC Laboratory Lubowa is accredited by College of American Pathologists (CAP). Samples were shipped to Biochemistry Laboratory of Mbarara University of Sciences and Technology (MUST) for preparation for serum zinc analysis. Serum zinc was analysed at Government Chemistry Analytical Laboratory, a facility with capacity for quality scientific and analytical services for different purposes.

3.6.4 Assay for serum zinc levels

Serum zinc levels was measured using atomic absorption spectrophotometry 200 Series AA AAS (Agilent Technologies, California USA) at the Government Chemistry Analytical Laboratory, Kampala-Uganda. A modified method by D'haese et al. (1992) and the Department of Nutrition, University of Otago, Laboratory protocol was used. In brief, serum samples and controls were diluted at 1:30 with sample diluent (5% HNO₃). To standard zinc

solutions in 5% HNO₃ was added glycerol (1:120) to match serum viscosity. Standards of known zinc concentrations were analyzed together with serum controls and samples. Unknown serum zinc concentrations were determined against a serum-matched calibration curve by extrapolation (appendix 6).

3.6.5 Assay for complete blood count (CBC)

Complete blood count (CBC) was measured following the method described by Karino et al. (2015) with modifications. Whole blood specimens collected in ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) tubes was used for this purpose. Measurements were made within 6 hours after collection. The assay was done by the PI with the help of a qualified laboratory technician using an automated haemalyser; Sysmex XN-350 (Sysmex, Asia green, Singapore) at Lancet Laboratories, Masaka.

3.6.6 Assay for IL-2 and IL-4 levels

Both IL-2 and IL-4 were quantified using Enzyme-Linked Immunosorbent Assay (ELISA) technique as described by Wang et al. (2015) with some modifications. The assays were carried out at the Joint Clinical Research Centre Laboratory, Lubowa-Kampala by the PI and a qualified laboratory technician. Briefly, serum was isolated from blood samples and diluted with sample diluents supplied with the kit prior to determination of IL-2 and IL-4. Serum IL-2 and IL-4 concentrations were determined using the Human IL-2 and Human IL-4 ELISA kits (MyBiosource.com, San Diego, USA), according to the manufacturer's protocol.

Briefly, 100µL of sample and standards of the two kits were pipetted into the 96-strip wells for IL-2 and IL-4. Standards and samples were run in duplicates. Absorbance was read at 450nm using a microplate reader to obtain the optical density (OD). Standard curves of mean absorbance of standard concentrations of IL-2 and IL-4 were plotted. The standard curves were used to determine the concentration of IL-2 and IL-4 in the study participants' samples.

3.6.7 C-reactive protein assay (CRP)

Blood samples were collected in clot activator tubes (SST). C-reactive protein levels were measured within 12 hours. The assay was done photometrically using an automated

Biochemical analyser; Architect c4000 (Abbott, Canon Medical Systems Corporation, Tochigi, Japan) following the standard operating procedures at Lancet Laboratory, Masaka Branch.

3.6.8. Serum albumin assay

Serum albumin was determined photometrically following the laboratory standard operating procedures using an Architect c4000 Clinical chemistry analyser (Abbott, Canon Medical Systems Corporation, Tochigi, Japan) at Lancet Laboratory Masaka Branch.

3.6.2 Quality control

Anthropometric measurements were repeated twice by the same person throughout the study. Beakers, volumetric flasks, pipette tips, Pasteur pipettes, falcon tubes and cryovials were acid-washed in 0.1N HCl to decontaminate them and rinsed thoroughly using ultra-pure de-ionised water (>18 OHM.CM). Powder-free gloves were used to prevent contamination. Instruments were recalibrated as per the laboratory standard operating procedures and manufacturer's instructions. Assays were run with positive and negative controls, where applicable. IL-2 and IL-4 ELISA samples were run in duplicates, serum zinc in triplicates to check for intra-assay variations. Data was recorded in both soft and hard copy form and saved on an external back-up device. Transposition errors during data entry were controlled by double-entering the data into Excel database.

3.7 Data management

3.7.1 Data entry and statistical analysis

Raw data was entered and coded into Microsoft Excel software and exported to Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20 for analysis. Independent variables were gender, and serum zinc levels. Outcome variables were anthropometric nutritional status, white blood cell count and differentials, IL-2 and IL-4 levels. Continuous variables: age, serum zinc levels, cell counts, and interleukin levels are presented as means \pm standard deviations (SD) while categorical variables: gender, diagnosis of illnesses at presentation are given as percentages. Student's t and Mann Whitney U tests were used to assess differences between categories.

Anthropometric nutritional status was established using the WHO child growth Standards for the height- and weight-for-age standard deviations and z scores (World Health Organisation, 2019). Z scores of <-3 SD for height-and weight-for-age were used to categorize a child as stunted or underweight respectively.

Serum zinc levels were corrected for inflammation using established study-specific correction factors to estimate the true serum zinc levels. Prevalence of children presenting with signs of zinc deficiency (stunted; sparse, easily pluckable, brown hair; and non-traumatic cheilitis/stomatitis) was computed as the percentage or proportion. The functional criteria, one based upon stigmata for zinc deficiency (including stunting height-for-age z scores), and uncorrected (for inflammation) serum zinc levels and corrected serum zinc levels.

Correlations between the independent variables and outcome variables were explored with bivariate analysis. Relationships between serum zinc levels and anthropometric nutritional status, white blood cell counts, IL-2 and IL-4 and/or signs of zinc deficiency were explored using Pearson's moment or Spearman's rank coefficient correlations as appropriate. Values are given with confidence intervals (CI) at 95%, and significance level at $p < 0.05$.

3.7.2 Treatment of serum zinc data.

Linear regression model of log-normal transformed serum zinc (sZn) levels and cRP levels was performed to obtain study-specific geometric mean ratio (sGMR) of sZn. The study specific correction factor (CF) was calculated as 1 divided by sGMR. Corrected serum zinc levels were obtained by multiplying sGMR with the uncorrected serum zinc levels.

$$\ln(sZn) = -2.896e^{-0.05} \times cRP + 4.107$$

GMR= 0.99997, CF =1/0.99997 ~ 1. The difference between corrected and uncorrected sZn was negligible.

3.8. Ethical considerations

The proposal was presented in the Department of Biochemistry and reviewed by the Faculty of Medicine Research Committee (FRC). Ethics approval was obtained from MUST Research

Ethics Committee and administrative clearance to conduct the study at Masaka RRH was obtained from the Hospital Director Masaka RRH prior to commencement of the study.

Study participation was voluntary. The PI and the research assistant introduced the study to the parent/caretaker of a potential child participant. The RA and PI obtained written informed consent from the child's parent/caretaker using a consent document designed in English (appendix 3) and translated in Luganda (appendix 4) before recruitment of the child into the study.

A separate room other than the admission unit was used to ensure privacy. Children were given unique study number identifiers. Except for the consent document, all the data collection tools had study numbers instead of child's names. To ensure that the results from this research informed practice and thereby maximizing the benefit to sick children and the hospital, test results were returned to clinicians. Where it was found that a study participant, at any stage of the research requires emergency or special treatment, the child was introduced to the clinicians who gave the needed care.

CHAPTER 4 RESULTS

4.1. Study Procedure/Profile.

Figure 4.1. Study Procedure. Flow chart illustrating recruitment and data collection procedure. 53 children screened were eligible, 13 declined or withdrew consent. 40 participants were part of the study, One sample was missing for serum analyses (serum albumin and cRP). 3 samples were of either unsuitable or insufficient volume for serum zinc analysis.

4.2 Sociodemographic and clinical characteristics of children under five

Forty children were recruited in this study with equal number of participants by gender. The overall mean age was 27.76 ± 10.58 months (95% C.I 24.37-31.14) and the range 12.03-49.93 months. Females were older ($p < 0.0029$; $t = 3.182$). There were fewer children aged ≤ 24 months (15/40) than those above 24 months of age. Among those ≤ 24 months, majority were males (10/15) while females were the majority (15/25) among those aged > 24 months. **Table 4.1** presents anthropometric and clinical diagnoses of study participants. More than a third

(13/40) of the children were undernourished and 22.5% (9/40) were stunted but with no statistically significant gender differences (**Table 4.1.**).

Table 4.1. Study participants' sociodemographic, anthropometry and clinical diagnoses on admission (Means and medians are reported, and gender-differences are analysed where required).

Characteristic	All participants (n=40)	Males (n=20)	Females (n=20)	P value
Median age in months, (minimum, maximum)	28.89 (12.03, 49.93)	19.87 (12.03, 40.03)	33.86 (14.73, 49.93)	0.0032 [#]
Median weight in kg, (minimum, maximum)	10.6 (6, 15)	10.10 (6, 15)	11 (6, 15)	0.5506 [#]
Median height in cm (minimum, maximum)	86.00 (65.00, 101.0)	84.00 (65.00, 96.70)	87.35 (71.00, 101.0)	0.79 [#]
Mean MUAC in cm, (SD)	14.89 (±1.738)	15.02 (±1.613)	14.76 (±1.888)	0.6487 [*]
Number of children stunted (%)	9 (22.5)	4 (20)	5 (25)	-
Number of children wasted	5 (12.5)	2 (10)	3 (15)	-
Other stigmata for zinc deficiency ^z	9 (22.5)			
Diagnoses				
Malaria, pneumonia, diarrhea, or combination (%)	32 (80)			
Others	8 (20)			

* Student's t-test, # Mann-Whitney U test, ^z other stigmata for zinc deficiency (other than stunting) include sparse/brown/easily pluckable hair, non-traumatic cheilitis and/or stomatitis. Significance at $p < 0.05$.

In addition, children ≤ 24 months were more undernourished (9/14) with a significantly lower MUAC ($P = 0.0003$, $t = 3.98$) (**Figure 4.2**).

Figure 4.2. Age category comparison for anthropometric measurements. A. bar chart for the number of children with Z scores <-3SD for H/A and W/H. **B.** Age-category comparison for the MUAC, Student's t test, *** P <0.001.

4.2 Hematological parameters

Table 2 presents means of hematological parameters among the under 5 children. Up to 15/40 (37.5%), 33/40 (82.5%) and 12/40 (30%) of the study participants had a lower count below laboratory reference ranges for reticulocyte count, hemoglobin concentration and mean corpuscular volume respectively. Of the 33 who had anemia, 8 (20%) were severely anemic (Hb <7.0 g/dL), 14 (35%) moderately anemic (Hb 7.0-10.10.9 g/dL) and 11 (27.5%) had mild anemia (Hb 10-10.9 g/dL). The proportion of children with macrocytosis were 8/40 (20%).

The proportion of participants with a lower white blood cell, neutrophils and lymphocytes count were 4/40 (10%), 2/40 (5%) and 24/40 (60%) respectively. Up to 6/40 (15%) had leukocytosis, 9/40 (22.5%), neutrophilia 2/40 (5%), lymphocytosis and 27/40 (67.5%) exhibited monocytosis. Children ≤ 24 months had high mean corpuscular hemoglobin (P=0.03, U=108.5), lymphocyte count (P=0.01, U=97) and monocyte count (P=0.01, U=97.5).

Table 4.2. Means and medians for different hematological indices of children.

Hematological parameters	Mean (±SD)	Median (5 th and 95 th percentile)	Reference range (Laboratory values) *
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Full blood count

Red blood cell count, $\times 10^6/\mu\text{L}$	3.75 (±1.025)	3.995 (3.57,4.31)	3.7–5.3
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Hemoglobin, g/dL	8.995 (\pm 2.365)	9.2 (8.5,10.6)	11–14
Mean corpuscular volume, fL	76.36 (\pm 13.33)	78.9 (72.5,82.6)	73–89
Mean corpuscular hemoglobin, pg	25.64 (\pm 9.325)	24.9 (22.9,26.3)	24–30
White blood cell count, $\times 10^3 \mu\text{L}$	12.97 (\pm 7.854)	10.61 (9.12,13.8)	6.0–17.5
Neutrophils, $\times 10^3 \mu\text{L}$	6.17 (\pm 4.61)	4.66 (2.91,6.31)	1.5–8.5
Lymphocytes $\times 10^3 \mu\text{L}$	4.692 (\pm 3.209)	3.70 (3.31,4.84)	4.0–13.5
Monocytes $\times 10^3 \mu\text{L}$	1.732 (\pm 1.327)	1.44 (0.94,2.18)	0.2–0.9
Eosinophils $\times 10^3 \mu\text{L}$	0.086 (\pm 0.121)	0.05 (0.01,0.08)	0.0–0.5
Basophils $\times 10^3 \mu\text{L}$	0.293 (\pm 0.797)	0.05 (0.04,0.09)	0.0–0.3

* *Lancet Laboratory, Masaka established reference ranges (paediatric)*

4.3 Serum biochemical parameters

The means of serum albumin, c-reactive protein and zinc levels for the participants are presented in Table 3. There was no statistically significant gender-based differences of the serum parameters. Additionally, the time of collection of blood specimens did not significantly affect the serum zinc levels (Table 4.3). The proportion of children with low albumin concentration below reference range (35–48 g/L) was 46.2% (18/39) and all study participants had high c-reactive protein (cRP) levels, above 5 mg/L. Serum albumin, cRP and zinc were not significantly different among children of both age categories.

Table 4.3. Means of serum biochemical parameters among under 5 children.

Serum, SI units	Mean (\pm SD)	Reference ranges	P value
Albumin^a, g/L	35.08 (\pm 9.67)		
Male	36.53 (\pm 3.31)	35-48 g/L	0.1413
Female	33.70 (\pm 7.53)		
c-Reactive Protein^{A,*}, mg/L	49.42 (\pm 2.58)	<5 mg/L	
Male	43.78(\pm 2.28)		0.5546
Female	55.44(\pm 2.90)		
Zinc[*], $\mu\text{g/dL}$	63.58 (\pm 19.89)	80-110 $\mu\text{g/dL}$ ⁺	
Male ^B	61.62(\pm 1.35)		0.7301
Female	62.76 (\pm 20.70)		
Time of collection[#]			
Morning	56.96 (\pm 17.0)		0.5437
Afternoon	64.26 (\pm 20.3)	-	

^{A, B} Geometric means ^a Student's t-test, *Mann-Whitney U test, [#] Welch' test. ⁺Acceptable lower cutoffs for children 10 years of <57 $\mu\text{g/dL}$ were considered.

4.4 Cytokine (IL-2 and IL-4) levels

Study participants had high levels of both interleukin (IL) 2 and IL-4; however, the difference in the means of the two cytokines was not statistically significant between the two genders (Table 4.4). No age category differences were observed for both cytokines.

Table 4.4. Cytokine parameters (IL-2 and IL-4 levels) for study participants and gender-based comparisons.

Cytokine, SI units	All participants	Males	Females	p value
IL-2 ^a , ng/L Mean (±SD)	153.9(±2.53)	216.6 (±2.60)	109.3 (±2.19)	0.0700*
IL-4, pg/mL Mean (±SD)	94.09 (±23.54)	89.26 (±22.2)	98.69 (±24.4)	0.2115 [#]

^aGeometric mean * Mann-Whitney U test, [#] Student's t-test

4.5 Prevalence of zinc deficiency

The prevalence of zinc deficiency based upon serum zinc levels was 40.6% (13/32); it was higher than that of the functional criteria (22.5%). Seven out of the thirteen (53.8%) who were zinc deficient were males. Using non-serum indicators of zinc deficiency, stunting was observed in 9 children (22.5%); a similar number presented with other stigmata (sparse brown or easily pluckable hair, non-traumatic cheilitis) commonly seen when there is acute zinc deficiency.

4.6 Association of serum zinc levels with hematological parameters

Table 5 summarizes the correlations between serum zinc levels and hematological parameters. Serum zinc was significantly correlated with total white blood cell and lymphocyte count (Table 4.5). In general, white blood cell, neutrophil, lymphocyte, and basophil counts were higher in children with normal sZn levels whereas monocyte and eosinophil counts were slightly higher for the zinc deficient group. The differences were not significant between the two groups (Appendix 12).

Table 4.5. Spearman's correlation of serum zinc and hematological parameters.

Hematological parameter	Correlation	P vlaue
White blood cell	0.41	0.02
Neutrophils	0.27	0.14
Lymphocytes	0.43	0.01
Monocytes	0.13	0.5
Eosinophils	-0.001	0.96
Basophils	0.34	0.06

4.7 Association of serum zinc with serum albumin and serum cRP levels

Serum zinc was not significantly associated with both serum albumin level and cRP (**Table 4.6**). Moreover, only four out of the thirteen (30.7%) study participants who were zinc deficient had low serum albumin level.

Table 4.6. Correlation between serum zinc and other studied serum parameters

Serum parameter	Correlation	P value
Albumin	-0.04	0.85
cRP	0.12	0.5
IL-2	0.30	0.09
IL-4*	0.05	0.8
Th1/Th2 ratio	0.11	0.5

* Pearson's correlation, others are Spearman's correlation.

Children with normal serum zinc had higher serum albumin than their counterparts. The difference, however, was not statistically significant. Conversely, serum cRP was higher among children with zinc deficiency, but not significantly different from those with normal sZn levels (**Appendix 12**).

4.8 Association between serum zinc levels, IL-2, IL-4 levels and Th1/Th2 ratio

Serum IL-2 and IL-4 as well as the Th1/Th2 ratio were not statistically significant correlated with serum zinc (**Table 4.6**).

CHAPTER 5 DISCUSSION

The main objective of this study was to determine the prevalence of zinc deficiency and assess the association between low serum zinc levels and the immune system in children aged 12 to 59 months admitted to the paediatrics ward of Masaka RRH. The discussion of the findings in this study focuses primarily on the prevalence of zinc deficiency, and secondly on the association of serum zinc levels with hematological parameters, blood albumin, interleukin (IL) 1 and IL2 among the study population.

5.1 Prevalence of zinc deficiency

Our study found a high prevalence of zinc deficiency in children under-5 being admitted to MRRH of 40.6%. This value lies within the range of prevalence of zinc deficiency of 20-70% by the Uganda Nutrition Action Plan 2011-2016 (Government of Uganda, 2017). Studies conducted elsewhere reported comparable prevalence.

A study among rural pre-school going children in South Africa reported a 42.5% prevalence of zinc deficiency (Motadi et al., 2015). In a recent review on whether low intakes of iron, vitamin A, iodine and zinc were of health concern in four sub-Saharan countries, pooled analysis reported zinc prevalence of 35% ,40% and 63% in Ethiopia, South Africa and Nigeria, respectively (Harika et al., 2017). The reason for similarity might be due to having similar health settings, living under nearly similar conditions (rural areas) and having similar risk factors to zinc deficiency like low dietary intakes of zinc and diseases like frequent diarrhoea. The high prevalence of zinc deficiency in sub-Sahara Africa is of public health concern.

Given a lower prevalence of functional zinc deficiency (stunted children being 22.5%) than the serum zinc determined prevalence of 40.6%, it may be concluded that most of the children possibly had an acute form of zinc deficiency prior to the illness event. While the current study population was in a hospital setting, a 22.5% prevalence is suggestive of low zinc values in the community among the under-5. The national prevalence of stunting is at 29% (USAID,

2018). These statistics are not good for a country whose rate of decline of malnutrition is very slow and is also aiming at achieving SDG 3 by 2030 (Adebisi et al., 2019).

An important issue emerging from the high prevalence of stunting is likely to impact the children's livelihood as it has been reported to contribute to poor cognitive development, poor school performance (Alam et al., 2020), poor audio-visual memory, behavioral problems like attention and concentrating difficulties (Adebisi et al., 2019) that may persist and impact into their adult lives (Alam et al., 2020). More than 10 years since the predictions, the situation is still bad and it has implications on achieving sustainable development goal (SDG 3), namely, ensuring good health and well-being for all. Raising awareness and increasing access to targeted health services is one of the ways that have been identified to achieve SDG 3. Unless more resources are available to meet this need, achieving this SDG by 2030 is nearly impossible.

5.2 Effect of serum zinc levels on hematological parameters

A high prevalence of anemia (82.5%) among the U5 children with a third having microcytosis and a fifth macrocytosis implies reduced intake of iron and folate and/or B12, respectively. This study did not determine the cause of the observed derangements; however, these red blood indices suggest that the observed zinc deficiency might be as a result of reduced intake as comparable observations have been found elsewhere (Motadi et al., 2015, Atasoy and Bugdayci, 2018, Palacios et al., 2020), and as well ZnD co-exists with anemia

Overall, the participants' red blood cell indices were lower than for 'normal' children in a previous study in eastern Uganda to establish paediatric reference ranges for children between 1 to 5 years (Kironde et al., 2013). The current study reports a higher prevalence of anemia than the country's estimates of 53.4% in children between 6-59 months (Nankinga et al., 2019). A recent study in Lira and Jinja referral hospitals revealed a comparable prevalence of severe anemia (25.2%) as one of the current study (20%) (Opoka, 2020). These statistics indicate a high prevalence of anemia among the under-5 in the community. Given the effects

of anemia and ZnD in children under-5, measures to explore the factors associated with anemia and ZnD, and interventions should be re-adjusted in the region for effectiveness.

5.2.1 White blood cells and serum zinc status

The correlation of sZn levels on the studied hematological parameters; white blood cell count and differential were of importance. In the current study, there was a positive correlation between sZn and white blood cell and lymphocyte counts an indication that sZn levels are vital in immune cell proliferation and/or growth. Moreover, it is the free zinc ions that have been reported earlier to be the biologically active form (Vallee and Falchuk, 1993, Wellinghausen and Rink, 1998). It is, therefore, not surprising that zinc deficiency has been reported to cause an overall decrease in peripheral blood immune cells (Maares and Haase, 2016).

However, some studies particularly in animals reported maintenance of the first line of defense that is the myeloid lineage cells of the innate system including polymorphonuclear granulocytes and monocytes (Ibrahim et al., 2017). This was observed in the current study where the number of neutrophils and monocytes were high amongst the study participants.

There are two possible explanations for this finding. Human monocytes and neutrophils have shorter lifespans of 1-7 days and 19 hours, respectively. However, during infection or other inflammatory challenges, marginating pools (from tissues for example bone marrow) replenish the circulating pool within minutes (Patel et al., 2017). At the same time, monocytes return from various tissues including the spleen which serves as a reservoir for monocytes (Patel et al., 2021). These mechanisms can be used for the maintenance of the two cells populations in the early phases of the illness in children.

In addition, zinc deficiency is largely known to be associated with a reduced number of lymphocytes (Maares and Haase, 2016), a similar finding in the current study. This is due to reduced maturation, differentiation and increased apoptosis of lymphocytes induced by zinc deficiency (Maares and Haase, 2016, Weyh et al., 2022).

It is not surprising that up to 80% of the study participants were diagnosed with the 'three most common diseases' known to be associated with zinc deficiency, that is, malaria, pneumonia and diarrhoea or a combination of any. This may be due to the dampening of the immune system associated with acute zinc deficiency.

Whereas it was observed in the current study that the innate system response was overall maintained during zinc deficiency, phagocytosis, generation of reactive oxygen species, generation of neutrophil extracellular traps (NETosis) and cytokine release become defective (Mayer et al., 2014).

5.3 Serum albumin, cRP and zinc levels

Serum albumin and cRP are commonly used as negative and positive indicators biomarkers of inflammation, respectively (Tsai et al., 2020) hypoalbuminemia and high cRP levels have been reported to result in poor outcomes in sick children with (Bhandarkar et al., 2019) indicating there is an existing relationship. Whereas there was a relationship (negative correlation between serum albumin and cRP) observed in this study, the association was not significant. This may be attributed to a smaller sample size for the current study compared to the large samples in the previous studies, in addition to differences in study settings.

Approximately 60 to 70% serum zinc is bound to albumin. This means that lower levels of albumin are likely to be associated with lower serum zinc levels as observed previously (Hennigar et al., 2018, McMillam and Rowe, 1982) in conditions resulting into a lower albumin concentration like inflammation causing a concomitant reduction of serum zinc concentration (Ghashut et al., 2016). In contrast, in the current study, the serum albumin was not statistically associated with serum zinc levels, a similar finding in a recent retrospective (chart-review) study among children aged 2 to 10 years (Sugawara et al., 2022).

Similarly, there was no correlation observed between serum cRP and zinc in the current study. A similar observation was reported in an earlier study where the difference in mean plasma zinc between non-infected and infected children was not significant (Brown, 1998). During

infection, zinc is redistributed into the liver under the influence of hepatic metallothionein which might explain the reduction in serum zinc levels as observed earlier (Karakochuk et al., 2017, Gebremedhin, 2020). As evidenced in previous clinical studies, the lack of significant association may be attributed to the stage and severity of infection (Beisel et al., 1971, Florea et al., 2018). In addition, a lower sample size is likely to have contributed to a lower study power and loss of associations in the current study.

In this current study, anemia was associated with markedly raised levels of cRP. The high levels of cRP in under 5 in this study and as well anemic is supported by findings from previous studies to explain the role of inflammation plays in the pathogenesis of SA (Opoka et al., 2020). Inflammation facilitates sequestration of iron, reduced iron uptake through hepcidin binding and reduces erythropoiesis in a chronic setting. These processes by reducing iron delivery to the bone marrow might be responsible for the anemia in the face of inflammation (Greffeuille et al., 2021).

5.4 Serum zinc levels and associated effects to IL-2 and -4

Assessment of T cell cytokines provides information on the activation status of the immune system. The current study evaluated the association of serum zinc levels and the activity of Th1 and Th2 T subset cells by studying some of their predominant cytokines. The levels of IL-2 and IL-4 cytokines produced by the study participants were higher when compared to a previous study Sciuca and Neamtu (2015) who reported lower levels in children with community acquired pneumonia (CAP) and wheezing. In addition, in the previous study, the participants had a single diagnosis of CAP, whilst in the current study, the majority of the participants had more than a single diagnosis at admission with the majority involving an infection. This might have resulted in an enhanced or overwhelming immune response among participants of the current study.

The high cRP levels observed in this study further explain the high level of inflammation. However, a previous study reported relatively high IL-2 and IL-4 levels in children with severe

and non-severe CAP (Haugen et al., 2015). Another study conducted among normal individuals aged 1-86 years observed lower levels of IL2 (10.5 pg/mL) and IL4 (6.2 pg/mL) in children aged 1-6 years (Kleiner et al., 2013). The ILs values are lower when compared to those in our study. This is because our study participants had either severe infections and/or mixed infections.

Overall, IL-2 levels are particularly higher than IL-4 due to the pleiotropic roles mediating both pro-inflammatory (promoting growth and development of cytotoxic T and natural killer cells and stimulating release of interferon gamma (IFN γ) and anti-inflammatory T regulatory cells (activating Tregs) (Glassman et al., 2021) during the immune response. IL-4 is a potent cytokine whose levels rise to either halt further synthesis of pro-inflammatory cytokines or neutralizing mechanisms of pro-inflammatory mediators (Ansar and Ghosh).

Zinc deficiency is known to cause an alteration in cytokine production of the Th1 and Th2 subsets, with a resultant impairment for the synthesis Th1 cytokines IFN- γ and IL-2, whereas TH2 cytokines IL-4, IL-6, and IL-10 potentially remain unaffected (Maywald et al., 2017). In a study by Sciuca and Neamtu (2015) the Th1/Th2 ratio for children with CAP was 0.7 which is interpreted as Th2 predominance. In contrast to this study, the Th1/Th2 ratio was 2.6, a higher value indicating a Th1 predominance and a highly inflammatory state (Yang et al., 2013) in the acute phase of infection. This may be supported by neutrophilia and monocytosis observed in the study. This is in contrast to studies which reported reduced Th1 cytokine production in zinc deficiency (Prasad, 2014a, Prasad, 2014b). The difference is possibly because, in the earlier study, changes were observed after a longer period of time of follow up (Prasad, 2000). The current study evaluated zinc deficiency in a hospital setting where such changes or shifts of the Th1/Th2 ratio had not yet happened suggesting that participants possibly had acute zinc deficiency.

5.5 Study limitations

Children were enrolled from one and a government hospital, which limits generalization of these results beyond the study population. However, being a Regional Referral Hospital, it receives patients from different socioeconomic backgrounds and a wide catchment area to provide important information on the subject under study. While having a control group would be desirable, there are ethical issues surrounding the use of healthy children in research. Therefore, not having a healthy control group makes it difficult to draw certain conclusions.

Furthermore, the time interval between the child's last meal and the time for blood collection, which is known to impact serum zinc concentrations was not recorded, however a non-fasting reference range was used in this study.

Single time point measurements of anthropometry and serum zinc might not be very informative to understand the reasons for the stunting and/or immune system derangements. The association of stunting with ZnD, growth patterns data is useful to estimate the proportion of children who are likely to be zinc deficient.

This study had a small sample size and blood specimens were collected once at admission, so it was not possible to detect possible variations in cytokine levels in relation to duration of infection. The total number of known cytokines are well over 100, but this study considered only IL-2 and IL-4; nevertheless, they are good representatives of the pro-inflammatory and anti-inflammatory cytokine interactions.

Despite these limitations, the findings here reveal a nutritional problem and deranged immune responses among children below 5 years of age and provides rationale for a larger community-based study or a longitudinal study with zinc supplementation.

CHAPTER 6 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.0 Conclusions

1. The study revealed a high prevalence of anemia and zinc deficiency among children aged 12 - 59 months admitted to the paediatric ward of Masaka RRH..
2. Zinc deficiency was associated with lymphopenia, but with a maintained number of white blood cell count and intact innate immunity. IL-2 was relatively lower in children with zinc deficiency, whereas IL-4 was less affected by zinc deficiency in the current study, leading to a relatively higher Th2 response in the early phase of infection.

6.1 Recommendations

1. Clinicians should regularly assess sick children aged 12-59 months for zinc deficiency and zinc supplementation be given as an intervention, where there is high suspicion of the deficiency. Intervention should be done not only for those suffering from diarrhoea and severe malnutrition, but all sick children with signs of ZnD.
2. More research in this area is required involving more health facilities including lower-level centers, a larger sample size preferably as regional surveys by the responsible authorities. These surveys should be longitudinal as single time point assessments in cross-sectional surveys do not correctly reflect the long-term process (like growth haltering due to zinc deficiency) and to monitor interventions. In addition, more cytokine biomarkers of adaptive immunity to be used to identify those that are consistent with zinc deficiency.

REFERENCES

- ABD EL-GHAFFAR, Y. S., SHOUMAN, A. E., HAKIM, S. A., EL GENDY, Y. G. A. & WAHDAN, M. M. M. 2022. Effect of Zinc Supplementation in Children Less Than 5 Years on Diarrhea Attacks: A Randomized Controlled Trial. *Global Pediatric Health*, 9, 2333794X221099266.
- ABDULHAMID, I., BECK, F., MILLARD, S., CHEN, X. & PRASAD, A. 2008. Effect of zinc supplementation on respiratory tract infections in children with cystic fibrosis. *Pediatric pulmonology*, 43, 281-287.
- ACEVEDO-MURILLO, J. A., GARCÍA LEÓN, M. L., FIRO-REYES, V., SANTIAGO-CORDOVA, J. L., GONZALEZ-RODRIGUEZ, A. P. & WONG-CHEW, R. M. 2019. Zinc supplementation promotes a Th1 response and improves clinical symptoms in fewer hours in children with pneumonia younger than 5 years old. A randomized controlled clinical trial. *Frontiers in pediatrics*, 7, 431.
- ADEBISI, Y. A., IBRAHIM, K., LUCERO-PRISNO, D. E., 3RD, EKPENYONG, A., MICHEAL, A. I., CHINEMELUM, I. G. & SINA-ODUNSI, A. B. 2019. Prevalence and Socio-economic Impacts of Malnutrition Among Children in Uganda. *Nutr Metab Insights*, 12, 1178638819887398.
- AFOLABI, O. F., SAKA, A. O., OJUAWO, A. & BILIAMINU, S. A. 2018. Serum zinc levels amongst under-five children with acute diarrhoea and bacterial pathogens. *Nigerian Postgraduate Medical Journal*, 25, 131.
- AHSAN, A. K., TEBHA, S. S., SANGI, R., KAMRAN, A., ZAIDI, Z. A., HAQUE, T. & ALI HAMZA, M. S. 2021. Zinc Micronutrient Deficiency and Its Prevalence in Malnourished Pediatric Children as Compared to Well-Nourished Children: A Nutritional Emergency. *Global Pediatric Health*, 8, 2333794X211050316.
- AKANLI, L., LOWENTHAL, D. B., GJONAJ, S. & DOZOR, A. J. 2003. Plasma and red blood cell zinc in cystic fibrosis. *Pediatric pulmonology*, 35, 2-7.
- ALAM, M. A., RICHARD, S. A., FAHIM, S. M., MAHFUZ, M., NAHAR, B., DAS, S., SHRESTHA, B., KOSHY, B., MDUMA, E., SEIDMAN, J. C., MURRAY-KOLB, L. E., CAULFIELD, L. E. & AHMED, T. 2020. Impact of early-onset persistent stunting on cognitive development at 5 years of age: Results from a multi-country cohort study. *PLoS One*, 15, e0227839.
- ALVES, C. X., DE BRITO, N. J., VERMEULEN, K. M., DANTAS LOPES, M. M., FRANÇA, M. C., BRUNO, S. S., ALMEIDA, M. & BRANDÃO-NETO, J. 2016. Serum zinc reference intervals and its relationship with dietary, functional, and biochemical indicators in 6- to 9-year-old healthy children. *Food Nutr Res*, 60, 30157.
- ANDREE, K. B., KIM, J., KIRSCHKE, C. P., GREGG, J. P., PAIK, H., JOUNG, H., WOODHOUSE, L., KING, J. C. & HUANG, L. 2004. Investigation of lymphocyte gene expression for use as biomarkers for zinc status in humans. *The Journal of nutrition*, 134, 1716-1723.
- ANSAR, W. & GHOSH, S. *Inflammation and Inflammatory Diseases, Markers, and Mediators: Role of CRP in Some Inflammatory Diseases*, Biology of C Reactive Protein in Health and Disease. 2016 Mar 24:67-107. doi: 10.1007/978-81-322-2680-2_4.
- ARENAS-RAMIREZ, N., WOYTSCHAK, J. & BOYMAN, O. 2015. Interleukin-2: biology, design and application. *Trends in immunology*, 36, 763-777.
- ATASOY, H. I. & BUGDAYCI, G. 2018. Zinc deficiency and its predictive capacity for anemia: Unique model in school children. *Pediatr Int*, 60, 703-709.
- BAFARO, E., LIU, Y., XU, Y. & DEMPSKI, R. E. 2017. The emerging role of zinc transporters in cellular homeostasis and cancer. *Signal transduction and targeted therapy*, 2, 17029.
- BANUPRIYA, N., BHAT, B. V., VICKNESHWARAN, V. & SRIDHAR, M. G. 2020. Effect of zinc supplementation on relative expression of immune response genes in neonates with sepsis: A preliminary study. *Indian J Med Res*, 152, 296-302.
- BAO, B., PRASAD, A. S., BECK, F. W., BAO, G. W., SINGH, T., ALI, S. & SARKAR, F. H. 2011. Intracellular free zinc up-regulates IFN- γ and T-bet essential for Th1 differentiation in Con-A stimulated HUT-78 cells. *Biochemical and biophysical research communications*, 407, 703-707.

- BARFFOUR, M. A., HINNOUHO, G. M., WESSELLS, K. R., KOUNNAVONG, S., RATSAVONG, K., SITTHIDETH, D., BOUNHEUANG, B., SENGNAM, K., CHANHTHAVONG, B., ARNOLD, C. D., BROWN, K. H., LARSON, C. P. & HESS, S. Y. 2020. Effects of therapeutic zinc supplementation for diarrhea and two preventive zinc supplementation regimens on the incidence and duration of diarrhea and acute respiratory tract infections in rural Laotian children: A randomized controlled trial. *J Glob Health*, 10, 010424.
- BATES, C., BATES, P., DARDENNE, M., PRENTICE, A., LUNN, P., NORTHROP-CLEWES, C., HOARE, S., COLE, T., HORAN, S. & LONGMAN, S. 1993. A trial of zinc supplementation in young rural Gambian children. *British Journal of Nutrition*, 69, 243-255.
- BEISEL, W. R., PEKAREK, R. S., VAN ORMER, D. & WANNEMACHER, R. W., JR. 1971. Influence of acute infection on the metabolism of zinc and other trace elements. *Psychopharmacol Bull*, 7, 34-5.
- BHANDARKAR, N., SAVE, S., BAVDEKAR, S. B., SISODIA, P. & DESAI, S. 2019. Serum Albumin and C-Reactive Protein as Predictors of Adverse Outcomes in Critically Ill Children: A Prospective Observational Pilot Study. *The Indian Journal of Pediatrics*, 86, 758-759.
- BHASKARAM, P. 2002. Micronutrient malnutrition, infection, and immunity: an overview. *Nutrition reviews*, 60, S40-S45.
- BITARAKWATE, E., MWOROZI, E. & KEKITIINWA, A. 2003. Serum zinc status of children with persistent diarrhoea admitted to the diarrhoea management unit of Mulago Hospital, Uganda. *African Health Sciences*, 3, 54-60.
- BLACK, R. E. 2003. Zinc deficiency, infectious disease and mortality in the developing world. *The Journal of nutrition*, 133, 1485S-1489S.
- BONAVENTURA, P., BENEDETTI, G., ALBARÈDE, F. & MIOSSEC, P. 2015. Zinc and its role in immunity and inflammation. *Autoimmunity reviews*, 14, 277-285.
- BRANDÃO-NETO, J., STEFAN, V., MENDONÇA, B. B., BLOISE, W. & CASTRO, A. V. B. 1995. The essential role of zinc in growth. *Nutrition research*, 15, 335-358.
- BROWN, K. H. 1998. Effect of infections on plasma zinc concentration and implications for zinc status assessment in low-income countries. *The American journal of clinical nutrition*, 68, 425S-429S.
- BROWN, M. A. & HURAL, J. 2017. Functions of IL-4 and control of its expression. *Critical Reviews™ in Immunology*, 37.
- CAREY, A., DUGGAN, C. & MOTIL, K. J. 2016. Chronic complications of short bowel syndrome in children. *Jensen C., Motil K., Hoppin & A.(Eds.). In Up To Date. Retrieved from <https://www.uptodate.com/contents/chronic-complications-of-short-bowel-syndrome-in-children>*
- CHASAPIS, C. T., LOUSIDOU, A. C., SPILIOPOULOU, C. A. & STEFANIDOU, M. E. 2012. Zinc and human health: an update. *Archives of toxicology*, 86, 521-534.
- COUSINS, R. J. 2010. Gastrointestinal factors influencing zinc absorption and homeostasis. *International Journal for Vitamin and Nutrition Research*, 80, 243.
- D'HAESE, P., LAMBERTS, L., VANHEULE, A. & DE BROE, M. 1992. Direct determination of zinc in serum by Zeeman atomic absorption spectrometry with a graphite furnace. *Clinical chemistry*, 38, 2439-2443.
- DARDENNE, M. 2002. Zinc and immune function. *European journal of clinical nutrition*, 56, S20.
- DATTA, D., NAMAZZI, R., CONROY, A. L., CUSICK, S. E., HUME, H. A., TAGOOLA, A., WARE, R. E., OPOKA, R. O. & JOHN, C. C. 2019. Zinc for Infection Prevention in Sickle Cell Anemia (ZIPS): study protocol for a randomized placebo-controlled trial in Ugandan children with sickle cell anemia. *Trials*, 20, 460.
- DE BENOIST, B., DARNTON-HILL, I., DAVIDSSON, L., FONTAINE, O. & HOTZ, C. 2007. Conclusions of the Joint WHO/UNICEF/IAEA/IZiNCG Interagency Meeting on Zinc Status Indicators. *Food and Nutrition Bulletin*, 28, S480-S484.

- DÜNKELBERG, S., MAYWALD, M., SCHMITT, A. K., SCHWERDTLE, T., MEYER, S. & RINK, L. 2020. The interaction of sodium and zinc in the priming of T cell subpopulations regarding Th17 and Treg cells. *Molecular nutrition & food research*, 64, 1900245.
- DURO, D., JAKSIC, T. & DUGGAN, C. 2008a. Multiple micronutrient deficiencies in a child with short bowel syndrome and normal somatic growth. *Journal of pediatric gastroenterology and nutrition*, 46, 461.
- DURO, D., KAMIN, D. & DUGGAN, C. 2008b. Overview of pediatric short bowel syndrome. *Journal of pediatric gastroenterology and nutrition*, 47, S33-S36.
- EASLEY, D., KREBS, N., JEFFERSON, M., MILLER, L., ERSKINE, J., ACCURSO, F. & HAMBIDGE, K. M. 1998. Effect of pancreatic enzymes on zinc absorption in cystic fibrosis. *Journal of pediatric gastroenterology and nutrition*, 26, 136-139.
- ELMADFA, I. & MEYER, A. L. 2019. The Role of the Status of Selected Micronutrients in Shaping the Immune Function. *Endocr Metab Immune Disord Drug Targets*, 19, 1100-1115.
- FARHAN, J., ANEELA, A., SAIFULLAH, S., MOHAMMED, A., NADEEM, H. & BUSHRA, A. 1969. Comparison of serum zinc levels between healthy and malnourished children. *Am J Clin Nutr*, 24, 1349-53.
- FLOREA, D., MOLINA-LÓPEZ, J., HOGSTRAND, C., LENGYEL, I., DE LA CRUZ, A. P., RODRÍGUEZ-ELVIRA, M. & PLANELLS, E. 2018. Changes in zinc status and zinc transporters expression in whole blood of patients with Systemic Inflammatory Response Syndrome (SIRS). *Journal of Trace Elements in Medicine and Biology*, 49, 202-209.
- GAMMOH, N. & RINK, L. 2017. Zinc in infection and inflammation. *Nutrients*, 9, 624.
- GEBREMEDHIN, S. 2020. Adjusting serum zinc concentration for inflammation based on the data of Malawian preschool children and women of reproductive age. *Nutrition*, 79-80, 110841.
- GHASHUT, R. A., MCMILLAN, D. C., KINSELLA, J., VASILAKI, A. T., TALWAR, D. & DUNCAN, A. 2016. The effect of the systemic inflammatory response on plasma zinc and selenium adjusted for albumin. *Clinical Nutrition*, 35, 381-387.
- GIBSON, R. S., HESS, S. Y., HOTZ, C. & BROWN, K. H. 2008. Indicators of zinc status at the population level: a review of the evidence. *Br J Nutr*, 99 Suppl 3, S14-23.
- GLASSMAN, C. R., SU, L., MAJRI-MORRISON, S. S., WINKELMANN, H., MO, F., LI, P., PÉREZ-CRUZ, M., HO, P. P., KOLIESNIK, I., NAGY, N., HNIZDILOVA, T., PICTON, L. K., KOVAR, M., BOLLYKY, P., STEINMAN, L., MEYER, E., PIEHLER, J., LEONARD, W. J. & GARCIA, K. C. 2021. Calibration of cell-intrinsic interleukin-2 response thresholds guides design of a regulatory T cell biased agonist. *eLife*, 10, e65777.
- GORDON, E., GORDON, R. & PASSAL, D. 1981. Zinc metabolism: basic, clinical, and behavioral aspects. *The Journal of pediatrics*, 99, 341-349.
- GOUDET, S. M., BOGIN, B. A., MADISE, N. J. & GRIFFITHS, P. L. 2019. Nutritional interventions for preventing stunting in children (birth to 59 months) living in urban slums in low- and middle-income countries (LMIC). *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*, 6, Cd011695.
- GOVERNMENT OF UGANDA. 2017. *Uganda Nutrition Action Plan, 2011-2016: Scaling Up Multi-sectoral Efforts to Establish a Strong Nutrition Foundation for Uganda's Development* [Online]. Government of Uganda. Available: https://nutrition.opm.go.ug/wp-content/uploads/2017/11/Uganda_NutritionActionPlan_Nov2011.pdf [Accessed 2018].
- GREFFEUILLE, V., FORTIN, S., GIBSON, R., ROHNER, F., WILLIAMS, A., YOUNG, M. F., HOUGHTON, L., OU, J., DIJKHUIZEN, M. A., WIRTH, J. P., LANDER, R. L., MCDONALD, C. M., SUCHDEV, P. S., BERGER, J. & WIERINGA, F. T. 2021. Associations between Zinc and Hemoglobin Concentrations in Preschool Children and Women of Reproductive Age: An Analysis of Representative Survey Data from the Biomarkers Reflecting Inflammation and Nutritional Determinants of Anemia (BRINDA) Project. *The Journal of Nutrition*, 151, 1277-1285.

- GRUBER, K., MAYWALD, M., ROSENKRANZ, E., HAASE, H., PLUMAKERS, B. & RINK, L. 2013. Zinc deficiency adversely influences interleukin-4 and interleukin-6 signaling. *Journal of biological regulators and homeostatic agents*, 27, 661-671.
- HAASE, H. & RINK, L. 2014. Zinc signals and immune function. *Biofactors*, 40, 27-40.
- HARIKA, R., FABER, M., SAMUEL, F., MULUGETA, A., KIMIYWE, J. & EILANDER, A. 2017. Are low intakes and deficiencies in iron, vitamin A, zinc, and iodine of public health concern in Ethiopian, Kenyan, Nigerian, and South African children and adolescents? *Food and nutrition bulletin*, 38, 405-427.
- HASSAN, A., SADA, K. K., KETHEESWARAN, S., DUBEY, A. K. & BHAT, M. S. 2020. Role of Zinc in Mucosal Health and Disease: A Review of Physiological, Biochemical, and Molecular Processes. *Cureus*, 12, e8197.
- HAUGEN, J., CHANDYO, R. K., BROKSTAD, K. A., MATHISEN, M., ULAK, M., BASNET, S., VALENTINER-BRANTH, P. & STRAND, T. A. 2015. Cytokine Concentrations in Plasma from Children with Severe and Non-Severe Community Acquired Pneumonia. *PLoS One*, 10, e0138978.
- HENNIGAR, S. R., LIEBERMAN, H. R., FULGONI III, V. L. & MCCLUNG, J. P. 2018. Serum zinc concentrations in the US population are related to sex, age, and time of blood draw but not dietary or supplemental zinc. *The Journal of Nutrition*, 148, 1341-1351.
- HESS, S. Y. 2017. National Risk of Zinc Deficiency as Estimated by National Surveys. *Food Nutr Bull*, 38, 3-17.
- HIMOTO, T. & MASAKI, T. 2018. Associations between Zinc deficiency and metabolic abnormalities in patients with chronic liver disease. *Nutrients*, 10, 88.
- IBRAHIM, M. K., ZAMBRUNI, M., MELBY, C. L. & MELBY, P. C. 2017. Impact of Childhood Malnutrition on Host Defense and Infection. *Clin Microbiol Rev*, 30, 919-971.
- IMDAD, A. & BHUTTA, Z. A. Global micronutrient deficiencies in childhood and impact on growth and survival: challenges and opportunities. Meeting Micronutrient Requirements for Health and Development, 2012. Karger Publishers, 1-10.
- INTERNATIONAL ZINC NUTRITION CONSULTATIVE GROUP. 2020. *Adjusting plasma or serum zinc concentrations for inflammation* [Online]. <https://www.izincg.org>: IZiNCG. Available: https://www.izincg.org/s/IZiNCG_Technical-Brief-BRINDA_20Apr2020_final.pdf [Accessed November 2022].
- INZAGHI, E., PAMPANINI, V., DEODATI, A. & CIANFARANI, S. 2022. The Effects of Nutrition on Linear Growth. *Nutrients*, 14.
- IVASHKIV, L. B. 2018. IFN γ : signalling, epigenetics and roles in immunity, metabolism, disease and cancer immunotherapy. *Nat Rev Immunol*, 18, 545-558.
- JAROSZ, M., OLBERT, M., WYSZOGRODZKA, G., MŁYNYEC, K. & LIBROWSKI, T. 2017. Antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects of zinc. Zinc-dependent NF- κ B signaling. *Inflammopharmacology*, 25, 11-24.
- JUNTTILA, I. S. 2018. Tuning the cytokine responses: an update on interleukin (IL)-4 and IL-13 receptor complexes. *Frontiers in immunology*, 9, 888.
- KAHMANN, L., UCIECHOWSKI, P., WARMUTH, S., MALAVOLTA, M., MOCCHEGIANI, E. & RINK, L. 2006. Effect of improved zinc status on T helper cell activation and TH1/TH2 ratio in healthy elderly individuals. *Biogerontology*, 7, 429-35.
- KAMBE, T., TSUJI, T., HASHIMOTO, A. & ITSUMURA, N. 2015. The physiological, biochemical, and molecular roles of zinc transporters in zinc homeostasis and metabolism. *Physiological reviews*.
- KARAKOCHUK, C., BARR, S., BOY, E., BAHIZIRE, E., TUGIRIMANA, P., AKILIMALI, P., HOUGHTON, L. & GREEN, T. 2017. The effect of inflammation on serum zinc concentrations and the prevalence estimates of population-level zinc status among Congolese children aged 6–59 months. *European journal of clinical nutrition*, 71, 1467-1470.

- KARINO, S., WILLCOX, B. J., FONG, K., LO, S., ABBOTT, R. & MASAKI, K. H. 2015. Total and differential white blood cell counts predict eight-year incident coronary heart disease in elderly Japanese-American men: the Honolulu Heart Program. *Atherosclerosis*, 238, 153-158.
- KASAL, D. N., LIANG, Z., HOLLINGER, M. K., O'LEARY, C. Y., LISICKA, W., SPERLING, A. I. & BENDELAC, A. 2021. A Gata3 enhancer necessary for ILC2 development and function. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*, 118.
- KIDO, T., ISHIWATA, K., SUKA, M. & YANAGISAWA, H. 2019. Inflammatory response under zinc deficiency is exacerbated by dysfunction of the T helper type 2 lymphocyte–M2 macrophage pathway. *Immunology*, 156, 356-372.
- KIKAFUNDA, J., AGABA, E. & BAMBONA, A. 2014. Malnutrition amidst plenty: an assessment of factors responsible for persistent high levels of childhood stunting in food secure Western Uganda. *African Journal of Food, Agriculture, Nutrition and Development*, 14, 2088-2113.
- KIKAFUNDA, J. K., WALKER, A. F., ALLAN, E. F. & TUMWINE, J. K. 1998. Effect of zinc supplementation on growth and body composition of Ugandan preschool children: a randomized, controlled, intervention trial. *The American journal of clinical nutrition*, 68, 1261-1266.
- KIM, B. & LEE, W. W. 2021. Regulatory Role of Zinc in Immune Cell Signaling. *Mol Cells*, 44, 335-341.
- KING, J. C. 2010. Does zinc absorption reflect zinc status? *International Journal for Vitamin and Nutrition Research*, 80, 300.
- KING, J. C., BROWN, K. H., GIBSON, R. S., KREBS, N. F., LOWE, N. M., SIEKMANN, J. H. & RAITEN, D. J. 2015. Biomarkers of Nutrition for Development (BOND)—zinc review. *The Journal of nutrition*, 146, 858S-885S.
- KING, J. C., SHAMES, D. M. & WOODHOUSE, L. R. 2000. Zinc homeostasis in humans. *The Journal of nutrition*, 130, 1360S-1366S.
- KIRONDE, F., SEKIKUBO, M., NAIWUMBWE, H., NAMUSOKE, F., BUWEMBO, W., KIWUWA, S., OKETCH, B., NOOR, R., CHILENGI, R. & MWOROZI, E. 2013. Hematology and blood serum chemistry reference intervals for children in Iganga district of Uganda. *Health*, 2013.
- KLEINER, G., MARCUZZI, A., ZANIN, V., MONASTA, L. & ZAULI, G. 2013. Cytokine levels in the serum of healthy subjects. *Mediators Inflamm*, 2013, 434010.
- KREBS, N. F. 2000. Overview of Zinc Absorption and Excretion in the Human Gastrointestinal Tract. *The Journal of Nutrition*, 130, 1374S-1377S.
- KREBS, N. F. 2013. Update on zinc deficiency and excess in clinical pediatric practice. *Annals of Nutrition and Metabolism*, 62, 19-29.
- KREBS, N. F. & HAMBIDGE, K. M. 2007. Complementary feeding: clinically relevant factors affecting timing and composition—. *The American journal of clinical nutrition*, 85, 639S-645S.
- KREBS, N. F., MILLER, L. V. & MICHAEL HAMBIDGE, K. 2014. Zinc deficiency in infants and children: a review of its complex and synergistic interactions. *Paediatrics and international child health*, 34, 279-288.
- KREBS, N. F., SONTAG, M., ACCURSO, F. J. & HAMBIDGE, K. M. 1998. Low plasma zinc concentrations in young infants with cystic fibrosis. *The Journal of pediatrics*, 133, 761-764.
- KREJCIE, R. V. & MORGAN, D. W. 1970. Determining sample size for research activities. *Educational and psychological measurement*, 30, 607-610.
- LAMBERT, S. A., JOLMA, A., CAMPITELLI, L. F., DAS, P. K., YIN, Y., ALBU, M., CHEN, X., TAIPALE, J., HUGHES, T. R. & WEIRAUCH, M. T. 2018. The human transcription factors. *Cell*, 172, 650-665.
- LI, J., CAO, D., HUANG, Y., CHEN, B., CHEN, Z., WANG, R., DONG, Q., WEI, Q. & LIU, L. 2022. Zinc Intakes and Health Outcomes: An Umbrella Review. *Front Nutr*, 9, 798078.
- LIAO, W., LIN, J.-X. & LEONARD, W. J. 2011. IL-2 family cytokines: new insights into the complex roles of IL-2 as a broad regulator of T helper cell differentiation. *Current opinion in immunology*, 23, 598-604.

- LIN, C.-N., WILSON, A., CHURCH, B. B., EHMAN, S., ROBERTS, W. L. & MCMILLIN, G. A. 2012. Pediatric reference intervals for serum copper and zinc. *Clinica Chimica Acta*, 413, 612-615.
- MA, T. X. & GAO, Y. 2020. New insights into roles of basophils in initiating T helper type 2 immunity. *Chin Herb Med*, 12, 14-18.
- MAARES, M. & HAASE, H. 2016. Zinc and immunity: An essential interrelation. *Archives of biochemistry and biophysics*, 611, 58-65.
- MAARES, M. & HAASE, H. 2020. A Guide to Human Zinc Absorption: General Overview and Recent Advances of In Vitro Intestinal Models. *Nutrients*, 12.
- MACDONALD, R. S. 2000. The role of zinc in growth and cell proliferation. *The Journal of nutrition*, 130, 1500S-1508S.
- MAQBOOL, A., SCHALL, J. I., ZEMEL, B. S., GARCIA-ESPANA, J. F. & STALLINGS, V. A. 2006. Plasma zinc and growth status in preadolescent children with cystic fibrosis. *Journal of pediatric gastroenterology and nutrition*, 43, 95-101.
- MARET, W. 2019. The redox biology of redox-inert zinc ions. *Free Radical Biology and Medicine*, 134, 311-326.
- MAVERAKIS, E., FUNG, M. A., LYNCH, P. J., DRAZNIN, M., MICHAEL, D. J., RUBEN, B. & FAZEL, N. 2007. Acrodermatitis enteropathica and an overview of zinc metabolism. *Journal of the American Academy of Dermatology*, 56, 116-124.
- MAXFIELD, L., SHUKLA, S. & CRANE, J. S. 2021. Zinc deficiency. *StatPearls [Internet]*. StatPearls Publishing.
- MAYER, L. S., UCIECHOWSKI, P., MEYER, S., SCHWERDTLE, T., RINK, L. & HAASE, H. 2014. Differential impact of zinc deficiency on phagocytosis, oxidative burst, and production of pro-inflammatory cytokines by human monocytes. *Metallomics*, 6, 1288-1295.
- MAYO-WILSON, E., JUNIOR, J. A., IMDAD, A., DEAN, S., CHAN, X. H. S., CHAN, E. S., JASWAL, A. & BHUTTA, Z. A. 2014. Zinc supplementation for preventing mortality, morbidity, and growth failure in children aged 6 months to 12 years of age. *The Cochrane Library*.
- MAYWALD, M., WESSELS, I. & RINK, L. 2017. Zinc signals and immunity. *International journal of molecular sciences*, 18, 2222.
- MCCOMB, S., THIRIOT, A., AKACHE, B., KRISHNAN, L. & STARK, F. 2019. Introduction to the immune system. *Immunoproteomics*. Springer.
- MCDONALD, C. M., SUCHDEV, P. S., KREBS, N. F., HESS, S. Y., WESSELLS, K. R., ISMAILY, S., RAHMAN, S., WIERINGA, F. T., WILLIAMS, A. M. & BROWN, K. H. 2020. Adjusting plasma or serum zinc concentrations for inflammation: Biomarkers Reflecting Inflammation and Nutritional Determinants of Anemia (BRINDA) project. *The American journal of clinical nutrition*, 111, 927-937.
- MCMILLAM, E. M. & ROWE, D. J. F. 1982. Plasma zinc-serum albumin correlation: relevance to assessment of zinc status in humans. *Clinical and Experimental Dermatology*, 7, 599-604.
- MITRA, S. & LEONARD, W. J. 2018. Biology of IL-2 and its therapeutic modulation: Mechanisms and strategies. *Journal of leukocyte biology*, 103, 643-655.
- MOCCHIGIANI, E., MALAVOLTA, M., MARCELLINI, F. & PAWELEC, G. 2006. Zinc, oxidative stress, genetic background and immunosenescence: implications for healthy ageing. *Immunity & Ageing*, 3, 6.
- MOH UGANDA 2016. Guidelines for integrated management of acute malnutrition in Uganda. Ministry of Health, Uganda.
- MOHAMMAD, M. K., ZHOU, Z., CAVE, M., BARVE, A. & MCCLAIN, C. J. 2012. Zinc and liver disease. *Nutrition in Clinical Practice*, 27, 8-20.
- MOKOMANE, M., KASVOSVE, I., MELO, E. D., PERNICA, J. M. & GOLDFARB, D. M. 2018. The global problem of childhood diarrhoeal diseases: emerging strategies in prevention and management. *Therapeutic advances in infectious disease*, 5, 29-43.

- MOTADI, S. A., MBHENYANE, X. G., MBHATSANI, H. V., MABAPA, N. S. & MAMABOLO, R. L. 2015. Prevalence of iron and zinc deficiencies among preschool children ages 3 to 5 y in Vhembe district, Limpopo province, South Africa. *Nutrition*, 31, 452-458.
- NANKINGA, O., AGUTA, D. & KABAHUMA, C. 2019. Trends and determinants of anemia in Uganda: further analysis of the Demographic and Health Surveys. *DHS Working Papers*.
- NEUFINGERL, N. & EILANDER, A. 2021. Nutrient Intake and Status in Adults Consuming Plant-Based Diets Compared to Meat-Eaters: A Systematic Review. *Nutrients*, 14.
- NEVE, J., GEFFEL, R. V., HANOCQ, M. & MOLLE, L. 1983. Plasma and erythrocyte zinc, copper and selenium in cystic fibrosis. *Acta Paediatrica*, 72, 437-440.
- NISTOR, N., CIONTU, L., FRASINARIU, O.-E., LUPU, V. V., IGNAT, A. & STREANGA, V. 2016. Acrodermatitis enteropathica: a case report. *Medicine*, 95.
- OFFICE OF DIETARY SUPPLEMENTS NIH. 2018. *Zinc - Fact Sheet for Health Professionals* [Online]. National Institute of Health. Available: <https://ods.od.nih.gov/factsheets/Zinc-HealthProfessional/#en1> [Accessed 2018].
- OPOKA, R. 2020. *Severe anemia in Ugandan children under 5 years: Implementation research on its prevalence, management and outcomes*. Makerere University.
- OPOKA, R. O., CONROY, A. L., WAISWA, A., WASSWA, R., TUMWINE, J. K., KARAMAGI, C. & JOHN, C. C. 2020. Severe Anemia Is Associated with Systemic Inflammation in Young Children Presenting to a Tertiary Hospital in Uganda. *Am J Trop Med Hyg*, 103, 2574-2580.
- PALACIOS, A. M., HURLEY, K. M., DE-PONCE, S., ALFONSO, V., TILTON, N., LAMBDEN, K. B., REINHART, G. A., FREELAND-GRAVES, J. H., VILLANUEVA, L. M. & BLACK, M. M. 2020. Zinc deficiency associated with anaemia among young children in rural Guatemala. *Matern Child Nutr*, 16, e12885.
- PARK, S.-G., CHOI, H.-N., YANG, H.-R. & YIM, J.-E. 2017. Effects of zinc supplementation on catch-up growth in children with failure to thrive. *Nutrition research and practice*, 11, 487-491.
- PATEL, A. A., GINHOUX, F. & YONA, S. 2021. Monocytes, macrophages, dendritic cells and neutrophils: an update on lifespan kinetics in health and disease. *Immunology*, 163, 250-261.
- PATEL, A. A., ZHANG, Y., FULLERTON, J. N., BOELEN, L., RONGVAUX, A., MAINI, A. A., BIGLEY, V., FLAVELL, R. A., GILROY, D. W. & ASQUITH, B. 2017. The fate and lifespan of human monocyte subsets in steady state and systemic inflammation. *Journal of Experimental Medicine*, 214, 1913-1923.
- PRASAD, A. S. 1995. Zinc: an overview. *Nutrition (Burbank, Los Angeles County, Calif.)*, 11, 93-99.
- PRASAD, A. S. 2000. Effects of zinc deficiency on Th1 and Th2 cytokine shifts. *J Infect Dis*, 182 Suppl 1, S62-8.
- PRASAD, A. S. 2009. Zinc: role in immunity, oxidative stress and chronic inflammation. *Current Opinion in Clinical Nutrition & Metabolic Care*, 12, 646-652.
- PRASAD, A. S. 2014a. Impact of the discovery of human zinc deficiency on health. *Journal of Trace Elements in Medicine and Biology*, 28, 357-363.
- PRASAD, A. S. 2014b. Zinc is an antioxidant and anti-inflammatory agent: its role in human health. *Frontiers in nutrition*, 1, 14.
- PRASAD, A. S. 2020. Chapter 1 - Clinical and immunological effects and biomarkers of zinc deficiency. In: PRASAD, A. S. & BREWER, G. J. (eds.) *Essential and Toxic Trace Elements and Vitamins in Human Health*. Academic Press.
- RINK, L. 2000. Zinc and the immune system. *Proceedings of the Nutrition Society*, 59, 541-552.
- ROLLES, B., MAYWALD, M. & RINK, L. 2018. Influence of zinc deficiency and supplementation on NK cell cytotoxicity. *Journal of Functional Foods*, 48, 322-328.
- ROOHANI, N., HURRELL, R., KELISHADI, R. & SCHULIN, R. 2013. Zinc and its importance for human health: An integrative review. *J Res Med Sci*, 18, 144-57.

- SALMENPERÄ, L., PERHEENTUPA, J., PAKARINEN, P. & SIIMES, M. A. 1994. Zinc supplementation of infant formula. *The American journal of clinical nutrition*, 59, 985-989.
- SCIUCA, S. & NEAMTU, L. Age-dependent levels of IL-2, IL-4 in children with community acquired pneumonia and wheezing. *European Respiratory Journal*, 2015. EUROPEAN RESPIRATORY SOC JOURNALS LTD 442 GLOSSOP RD, SHEFFIELD S10 2PX, ENGLAND.
- SCRIMGEOUR, A. G. & CONDLIN, M. L. 2009. Zinc and micronutrient combinations to combat gastrointestinal inflammation. *Current Opinion in Clinical Nutrition & Metabolic Care*, 12, 653-660.
- SEKLER, I., SENSI, S. L., HERSHFINKEL, M. & SILVERMAN, W. F. 2007. Mechanism and regulation of cellular zinc transport. *Molecular medicine*, 13, 337.
- SHANKAR, A. H. & PRASAD, A. S. 1998. Zinc and immune function: the biological basis of altered resistance to infection. *The American journal of clinical nutrition*, 68, 447S-463S.
- SINGH, S. & DUBEY, R. P. 2019. Zinc, and its essentiality for human health. *The Pharma. Innov. Journal*, 8, 137-139.
- SKRAJNOWSKA, D. & BOBROWSKA-KORCZAK, B. 2019. Role of Zinc in Immune System and Anti-Cancer Defense Mechanisms. *Nutrients*, 11.
- SUGAWARA, D., MAKITA, E., MATSUURA, M. & ICHIHASHI, K. 2022. The Association Between Serum Zinc Levels and Anthropometric Measurements and Nutritional Indicators in Children With Idiopathic Short Stature. *Cureus*, 14.
- THOMPSON, M. W. 2022. Regulation of zinc-dependent enzymes by metal carrier proteins. *Biometals*, 35, 187-213.
- TIDEMANN-ANDERSEN, I., ACHAM, H., MAAGE, A. & MALDE, M. K. 2011. Iron and zinc content of selected foods in the diet of schoolchildren in Kumi district, east of Uganda: a cross-sectional study. *Nutr J*, 10, 81.
- TRAN, C. D., KATSIKEROS, R., MANTON, N., KREBS, N. F., HAMBIDGE, K. M., BUTLER, R. N. & DAVIDSON, G. P. 2011. Zinc homeostasis and gut function in children with celiac disease-. *The American journal of clinical nutrition*, 94, 1026-1032.
- TSAI, C.-M., YU, H.-R., TANG, K.-S., HUANG, Y.-H. & KUO, H.-C. 2020. C-reactive protein to albumin ratio for predicting coronary artery lesions and intravenous immunoglobulin resistance in Kawasaki disease. *Frontiers in pediatrics*, 8, 607631.
- UBOS AND ICF. 2017. *Uganda Demographic and Health Survey 2016: Key Indicators Report* [Online]. Uganda Bureau of Statistics (UBOS), and Rockville, MD: UBOS and ICF Kampala. Available: <https://dhsprogram.com/publications/publication-fr333-dhs-final-reports.cfm> [Accessed 2018].
- UGANDA MINISTRY OF HEALTH. 2019. *Masaka Regional Referral Hospital* [Online]. MoH. Available: <https://www.health.go.ug/sermon/masaka-regional-referral-hospital/> [Accessed 2021].
- UNITED NATIONS CHILDREN'S FUND/WORLD HEALTH ORGANIZATION/WORLD BANK GROUP. 2018. *WHO, World Bank Group. Levels and trends in child malnutrition. Joint child malnutrition estimate. Key findings of the 2018 edition* [Online]. World Health Organisation. Available: https://www.who.int/nutrition/publications/jointchildmalnutrition_2018_estimates/en/ [Accessed 2019].
- USAID. 2018. *Uganda: Nutrition Profile* [Online]. U.S. Aid for International Development. Available: <https://www.usaid.gov/sites/default/files/documents/1864/Uganda-Nutrition-Profile-Apr2018-508.pdf> [Accessed June 2021].
- VALLEE, B. L. & FALCHUK, K. H. 1993. The biochemical basis of zinc physiology. *Physiological reviews*, 73, 79-118.
- VAN BIERVLIET, S., VELDE, S. V., VAN BIERVLIET, J.-P. & ROBBERECHT, E. 2008. The effect of zinc supplements in cystic fibrosis patients. *Annals of Nutrition and Metabolism*, 52, 152-156.

- VAN WOUWE, J. 1989. Clinical and laboratory diagnosis of acrodermatitis enteropathica. *European journal of pediatrics*, 149, 2-8.
- VIVIER, E., RAULET, D. H., MORETTA, A., CALIGIURI, M. A., ZITVOGEL, L., LANIER, L. L., YOKOYAMA, W. M. & UGOLINI, S. 2011. Innate or adaptive immunity? The example of natural killer cells. *science*, 331, 44-49.
- WALRAVENS, P. A. 1979. Zinc metabolism and its implications in clinical medicine. *Western Journal of Medicine*, 130, 133.
- WANG, K., ZHOU, B., KUO, Y.-M., ZEMANSKY, J. & GITSCHIER, J. 2002. A novel member of a zinc transporter family is defective in acrodermatitis enteropathica. *The American Journal of Human Genetics*, 71, 66-73.
- WANG, L. & SONG, Y. 2018. Efficacy of zinc given as an adjunct to the treatment of severe pneumonia: A meta-analysis of randomized, double-blind and placebo-controlled trials. *The clinical respiratory journal*, 12, 857-864.
- WANG, R.-S., JIN, H.-X., SHANG, S.-Q., LIU, X.-Y., CHEN, S.-J. & JIN, Z.-B. 2015. Associations of IL-2 and IL-4 expression and polymorphisms with the risks of mycoplasma pneumoniae infection and asthma in children. *Archivos de Bronconeumología (English Edition)*, 51, 571-578.
- WANI, A. L., PARVEEN, N., ANSARI, M. O., AHMAD, M. F., JAMEEL, S. & SHADAB, G. 2017. Zinc: An element of extensive medical importance. *Current Medicine Research and Practice*, 7, 90-98.
- WELLINGHAUSEN, N. & RINK, L. 1998. The significance of zinc for leukocyte biology. *J Leukoc Biol*, 64, 571-7.
- WESSELLS, K. R. & BROWN, K. H. 2012. Estimating the global prevalence of zinc deficiency: results based on zinc availability in national food supplies and the prevalence of stunting. *PloS one*, 7, e50568.
- WESSELS, I., MAYWALD, M. & RINK, L. 2017. Zinc as a Gatekeeper of Immune Function. *Nutrients*, 9.
- WESSELS, I., ROLLES, B. & RINK, L. 2020. The Potential Impact of Zinc Supplementation on COVID-19 Pathogenesis. *Front Immunol*, 11, 1712.
- WEYH, C., KRÜGER, K., PEELING, P. & CASTELL, L. 2022. The Role of Minerals in the Optimal Functioning of the Immune System. *Nutrients*, 14.
- WHO 2013. *Guideline: updates on the management of severe acute malnutrition in infants and children*, World Health Organization.
- WIERINGA, F. T., DIJKHUIZEN, M. A., FIORENTINO, M., LAILLOU, A. & BERGER, J. 2015. Determination of zinc status in humans: which indicator should we use? *Nutrients*, 7, 3252-63.
- WONG, C. P. & HO, E. 2012. Zinc and its role in age-related inflammation and immune dysfunction. *Molecular nutrition & food research*, 56, 77-87.
- WORLD HEALTH ORGANISATION. 2013. *Research for universal health coverage: World health report 2013* [Online]. World Health Organisation. Available: <https://www.who.int/whr/2013/report/en/> [Accessed 2018].
- WORLD HEALTH ORGANISATION. 2018. *Zinc supplementation and growth in children* [Online]. Available: https://www.who.int/elena/titles/zinc_stunting/en/ [Accessed September 25 2019].
- WORLD HEALTH ORGANISATION. 2019. *Child growth standards; The WHO Child Growth Standards* [Online]. World Health Organisation. Available: <https://www.who.int/childgrowth/standards> [Accessed 2019].
- WORLD HEALTH ORGANIZATION. 2002. *The world health report 2002: reducing risks, promoting healthy life* [Online]. World Health Organization. Available: <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/67454> [Accessed 2018].
- WORLD HEALTH ORGANIZATION. 2013. *Pocket book of hospital care for children: guidelines for the management of common childhood illnesses* [Online]. World Health Organization. Available: <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/81170> [Accessed September 25 2019].

- XIA, P., LIAN, S., WU, Y., YAN, L., QUAN, G. & ZHU, G. 2021. Zinc is an important inter-kingdom signal between the host and microbe. *Veterinary Research*, 52, 39.
- YANG, W. C., HWANG, Y. S., CHEN, Y. Y., LIU, C. L., SHEN, C. N., HONG, W. H., LO, S. M. & SHEN, C. R. 2017. Interleukin-4 Supports the Suppressive Immune Responses Elicited by Regulatory T Cells. *Front Immunol*, 8, 1508.
- YANG, Y.-L., PAN, Y.-Q., HE, B.-S. & ZHONG, T.-Y. 2013. Regulatory T cells and Th1/Th2 in peripheral blood and their roles in asthmatic children. *Translational Pediatrics*, 2, 27.
- YESHAW, Y., WORKU, M. G., TESSEMA, Z. T., TESHALE, A. B. & TESEMA, G. A. 2020. Zinc utilization and associated factors among under-five children with diarrhea in East Africa: A generalized linear mixed modeling. *PLoS One*, 15, e0243245.
- ZHANG, L., ZENG, L., GUI, G., DUAN, Y. & HU, Z. 2015. Chapter 10 - Zinc Supplementation for Infants and Children with HIV Infection. *In: WATSON, R. R. (ed.) Health of HIV Infected People*. Boston: Academic Press.

APPENDICES

Appendix 1: MUST-REC Ethical Approval

MBARARA UNIVERSITY OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY
P.O. Box 1410, Mbarara Uganda. Tel: +256 485433795; Fax: +256 4854 20782
RESEARCH ETHICS COMMITTEE
E-mail: sec.rec@must.ac.ug

Our Ref: MUREC 1/7

Date: October 12, 2021

Dr. Male Keneth
Post graduate student

Re: Request for renewal and amendment of approved protocol on: "Zinc deficiency: Prevalence and effect of low serum zinc level on the immunity of children admitted on the pediatric ward of MRRH" 21/07-19

Type: Initial Application
 Protocol Amendment
 Letter of Amendment (LOA)
 Continuing Review
 Material Transfer Agreement
 Other, specify: _____

Your request for continuing review application and to amend the above mentioned study protocol has been received and reviewed by MUST REC.

Renewal has been granted up to **November 23, 2022**.

The following proposed amendments have been approved:

1. To change study site to Masaka Regional Referral Hospital
2. To change study title to: *Prevalence of zinc deficiency and association between low serum zinc and the immunity of children admitted on the Pediatric Ward of Masaka Regional Referral Hospital.*
3. to revise the sample size estimation to 40 children
4. add serum albumin to aid evaluation of variation of serum zinc with albumin
5. update study time frame and budget

The following is the list of documents approved in this amendment

Document	Language	Version
Proposal	English	September 2021
Informed consent forms	English, Luganda	September, 2021

I wish you all the best.

DR. BAJUNIRWE FRANCIS
CHAIR,
MUST RESEARCH ETHICS COMMITTEE

Appendix 2: Masaka Regional Referral Hospital Administrative

General Line: 0481-420018
Causality Dept: 038-2274346
Maternity: 038-2274340
Private wing: 0481-432395
Fax line: 0481-421343
E-mail: masakarrh@gmail.com

MASAKA REGIONAL REFERRAL HOSPITAL
P.O. BOX 18
MASAKA
Uganda

THE REPUBLIC OF UGANDA

MINISTRY OF HEALTH

For any correspondence on this Subject, please quote: **ADM. 170/06** Date: **16/09/2021**

Dr. Male Keneth
Mbarara University of Science and Technology
P.O BOX 1410
Mbarara

PERMISSION TO CARRY OUT DATA COLLECTION

The Research and Ethics Committee of Masaka Regional Referral Hospital reviewed your letter requesting to do data collection and research on a Study.

"PREVALENCE OF ZINC DEFICIENCY AND ASSOCIATION BETWEEN LOW SERUM ZINC AND THE IMMUNITY OF CHILDREN ADMITTED ON THE PEDIATRIC WARD OF MASAKA REGIONAL REFERRAL HOSPITAL."

Masaka Regional Referral Hospital is very glad to inform you that your request has been accepted.

Thank you for having interest in this hospital and we wish you success in this exercise.

Thanks,

Edward Kabuye
For: HOSPITAL DIRECTOR

Mission statement: To increase access of all people in Masaka region to quality, general & specialized services

Appendix 3: Consent form English Version

MBARARA UNIVERSITY OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY
RESEARCH ETHICS COMMITTEE
P.O. Box 1410, Mbarara, Uganda
Tel. 256-4854-33795 Fax: 256 4854 20782
Email : rec@must.ac.ug Web site : www.must.ac.ug

INFORMED CONSENT DOCUMENT

This document outlines the research study and expectations for potential participants. It should be written in layman terms and typed on MUST-REC letterhead. The wording should be directed to the potential participant NOT to REC. If a technical term must be used, define it the first time it is used. Also, any abbreviation should be spelled out the first time it is used.

NB: All the sections of this document must be completed without any editing or deletions
Please use a typing font that is easily distinguishable from the questions of the form

Study Title: *It should be the same as on all other documents related to the study*

Prevalence of Zinc Deficiency and Association Between Low Serum Zinc and The Immunity of Children Admitted on the Pediatric Ward of Masaka Regional Referral Hospital **Principal Investigator(s):** Dr. Male Keneth

I, Keneth Male, and my supervisors Dr. Gertrude Kiwanuka and Dr. Atwiine Barnabas of Mbarara University of Science and Technology are inviting you to participate in a research study that will involve children admitted to the Pediatric Ward of Masaka Regional Referral Hospital. We request that you give us some time to talk to you about this research.

INTRODUCTION

What you should know about this study:

- You are being asked to join a research study.
- This consent form explains the research study and your part in the study
- Please read it carefully and take as much time as you need
- You are a volunteer. You can choose not to take part and if you join, you may quit at any time. There will be no penalty if you decide to quit the study

Provide here a brief background to the study

Zinc is an element (or substance that cannot be separated into simpler substances) required by the body in very small amounts. It is essential for normal growth. It signals the cells that the body uses to protect itself against infections, to develop, divide, mature in order to carry out their functions. Zinc is important in brain function, and in the development of children. Zinc deficiency is a condition where one has a low amount of zinc in the body measured as low blood zinc level. It is an important cause of morbidity in developing countries and among the common deficiencies associated with malnutrition, in particular among young children. Unfortunately, zinc deficiency is not easily diagnosed. Although there are reports indicating that Uganda has many undernourished children, information about zinc deficiency among young children is very scanty. Children in many low-income countries including Uganda are at increased risk of illness and death from preventable infectious diseases. The likely contribution of zinc deficiency in children who are admitted to the

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APPROVED CONSENT IRB VERSION NUMBER: September 2014

PI NAME: Male Keneth

IRB NO: 21107-19

Children's ward of Masaka Regional Referral Hospital is not known. A common practice in many Hospitals is to give undernourished children and those with diarrhea zinc supplements. This study intends to establish the proportion of children admitted to the Children's ward of MRRH who are zinc deficient. This research will also investigate if the ability to fight against infections such as malaria and pneumonia is compromised in those children who are zinc deficient. It is expected that results from this study will provide information on zinc deficiency in the region to guide management of sick children in the area.

Purpose of the research project: *Include a statement that the study involves research, estimated number of participants, an explanation of the purpose(s) of the research procedure and the expected duration of the subject's participation.*

The purpose of this research is to determine the occurrence of zinc deficiency among children admitted at Masaka Regional Referral Hospital, and the effect of low blood zinc levels on the body's ability to fight infections. The research will involve 40 children aged between 12 months and 59 months. We are interested in this age group because it is a very important period of child development especially of the brain. You and your child will be expected to participate in this study for about one hour on the day the child is admitted.

Why you are being asked to participate: *Explain why you have selected the individual to participate in the study.*

You are being asked to participate because you are a parent/guardian of a sick child aged between 12 and 59 months admitted to the Children's Ward. We would like to know the level of zinc in the blood of your child to help us understand if the amount of zinc is related to the child's ability to fight infections.

Procedures: *Provide a description of the procedures to be followed and identification of any procedures that are experimental, clinical etc. If there is need for storage of biological (body) specimens, explain why, and include a statement requesting for consent to store the specimens and state the duration of storage.*

If you are willing to have your child participate in this research, we shall measure the child's weight, height and around the middle upper part of the arm. These measurements are commonly done to assess the growth pattern and nutrition grading of children. We request you allow us to take a little blood, about one teaspoonful, from your child's arm. This blood will be used to measure the amount of zinc in the child's blood and determine the number of cells and other substances which the body uses to fight against diseases. In case there is a need for blood for other investigations as determined by the attending doctor, the little blood needed for this study will be obtained from what the doctor will have drawn and so we shall not need to make a separate draw of blood. This blood will only be used for the purpose of this research.

Risks/discomforts: *Describe any reasonably foreseeable risks or discomforts-physical, psychological, social, legal or other associated with the procedure, and include information about their likelihood and seriousness. Discuss the procedures for protecting against or minimizing any potential risks to the subject. Discuss the risks in relation to the anticipated benefits to the subjects and to society.*

Your child is likely to feel a bit uncomfortable when taking weight and height measurements since weighty clothes will be taken off but we will do whatever is possible to do it fast. The feeling is not

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any different what is commonly experienced when such measurements are done Your child will feel some pain when collecting the blood specimen and there will be a little bleeding at the collection site, but only for a short time. The bleeding from the collection site will be controlled by pressing the area with clean cotton wool. We shall ensure that qualified clinicians who usually draw blood do this. To protect your child against any possible infections, we shall use a new, disposable sterile needle and syringe. We do not foresee any risk to you.

Benefits: Describe any benefits to the subject or other benefits that may reasonably be expected from the research. If the subject is not likely to benefit personally from the experimental protocol note this in the statement of benefits.

Results obtained from body measurements and from analyzing blood samples will be used by the doctors attending to your child. If during the study, it is discovered that your child requires special treatment, you will be introduced to the clinician who will help give it. In addition, the information about the child's blood level of zinc and how it is associated with the body's ability to fight disease would be useful in designing measures to improve quality of health care services offered to children.

Incentives/rewards for participating: It is assumed that there are no costs to subjects enrolled in research protocols. Any payments to be made to the subject (e.g., travel expenses, token of appreciation for time spent) must also be stated, including when the payment will be made.

You will not be given any money for your participation or that of your child. You will receive a bar of soap and kilogram of sugar as compensation for your time.

Protecting data confidentiality: Provide a statement describing the extent, if any, to which confidentiality or records identifying the subjects will be maintained. If data is in form of tape recordings, photographs, movies or videotapes, researcher should describe period of time they will be retained before destruction. Showing or playing of such data must be disclosed, including instructional purposes.

We shall ensure that all the information you will give to us and what we shall obtain from the procedures related to this research will be kept confidential. To achieve this, we will not write either your name or your child's name on the laboratory form for this study. We shall give your child a study number which will be used on all his/her documents. Only this document seeking your permission to allow your child to participate in this research will bear your name and that of the child. However, this informed consent will be kept separately the laboratory forms such that it will not be possible to link the results bearing only a study number with this form. The documents will be locked up in drawers in the investigator's office. No other person except the research team will have access to these documents. The results from the analyzing blood sample will be available to the doctors attending to the child and will be kept in the child's hospital file. However, even with all this in place, it is possible to have a small breach of this commitment to confidentiality such as when the Committee that oversees research and ensures the protection of participants' rights requests to see the documents. In the unlikely event that this happens, we shall ensure that only those entrusted with this responsibility access the necessary information.

Protecting subject privacy during data collection: Describe how this will be ensured.

Your consent will be obtained in privacy taking care that other people do not hear what you tell us. Again, your name will not be used on other documents except the consent form.

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	PI NAME: NAME KENYA
	IRB NO: 21107-19

Right to refuse/withdraw: Include a statement that participation is voluntary, refusal to participate will involve no penalty or loss of benefits to which the subject is otherwise entitled.

Your child's participation is voluntary. You are free to participate or not to, and you are free to withdraw from the study any time you wish. If there is a question you do not feel comfortable answering, you can tell me and we skip it.

What happens if you leave the study? Include a statement that the subject may discontinue participation at any time without penalty or loss of benefits.

You and the child are free to leave the study at any time. This will not affect in any way the treatment or care you are to receive. You will be excluded from the study and the information that will have been obtained from you shall not be included in the final analysis. There are no penalties for withdrawing from the study.

Who do I ask/call if I have questions or a problem? Include contact for researcher or Faculty advisor and Chairman MUST-REC

Investigator contacts	Contact for REC office
Dr. Male Keneth Mbarara University of Science and Technology Department of Biochemistry Tel: 0701 291245	Dr. Francis Bajunirwe Chairman MUST-REC P.O Box 1410 Mbarara Tel: 0485 433795

What does your signature (or thumbprint/mark) on this consent form mean?

Your signature on this form means

- You have been informed about this study's purpose, procedures, possible benefits and risks
- You have been given the chance to ask questions before you sign
- You have voluntarily agreed to be in this study

_____	_____	_____
Print name of adult participant	Signature of adult participant/legally Authorized representative	Date
_____	_____	_____
Print name of person obtaining Consent	Signature	Date
_____	_____	_____
Thumbprint/mark	signature of witness	Date

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Appendix 4: Consent Form Luganda version

MBARARA UNIVERSITY OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY
Akakiiko ketendekero akalondoola ku by'okunonyereza (REC)
P.O. Box 1410, Mbarara, Uganda
Tel. 256-4854-33795 Fax: 256 4854 20782
Email: rec@must.ac.ug Web site : www.must.ac.ug

FOOMU Y'OKUMANYISIBWA

FOOMU Y'OKUMANYISIBWA OKUKIRIZA OKWETABA MUKUNONYEREZA KUNO

Omutwe gwebinonyerezebwo: Obungi bw'abaana abatalina munyo gwa 'zinc' ggumala: nebibaaawo nga omunyo ggwa zinc mutono mumusaayi ku engeri emibiri ggy'abaana gyegirwanyisa endwadde mwabo abaana abaweebwa ebitanda mu ddwaliro ekkulu erye Masaka.

Omunonyereza omukulu:

Dr. Keneth Male, MBChB, MSc. BIOCHEMISTRY (omuyizi w'essomo lyawaggulu)

Omulabirizi:

Associate Professor Gertrude Kiwanuka, PhD ne Dr. Barnabas Atwiine, FPHO, MMED

ENNYANJULA

BYOLINA OKUMANYA KUKUNONYEREZA KUNO:

- Osabibwa okwetaba mu kunonyereza kuno
- Foomu eno ennyonyola kukunonyereza kuno n'omugaso gw'okwetabamu kwo.
- Foomu eno gisome n'obwegendereza era twala obudde bwonna bwewetaaga.
- Okwetaba mu kunonyereza kuno kusalawo kwo. Osobola obutetabamu. So nga ate bwewetaabamu, okyasobola okuguvaamu akasera konna woyagalidde. Tewali kibonerezo kyonna kijja kuweebwa singa osalawo okuvamu mumusomo gunno.

Entandikiro n'enyanjula yokunonyereza.

Zinc munnyo ogwetagisibwa mumubiri mukipimo kitono ddala. Ekirungo kino kyetagibwa nnyo okukula obulungi. Zinc kirisa ekiyamba obutofaali bwomumubiri okukula n'omukulwanisa endwadde. Omunyo gwa zinc gwankizo munkola y'obwongo nokukula kwabaana.. ~~Kugira~~ Omunyo gwa zinc okuba omutono mumubiri kiva kukulya obyokulya ebitayina munnyo ggwa zinc gumala. Era abaana abli mumawanga agakyakula basangibwa nga tebalina munnyo ggwa zinc gumala. Naye ate embeera eno teragulwa basaswo. Zalipoota eziriwo ziraga nti Uganda tulina abaana abalwaala obulwadde bwendya embi, naye obubaka obututegeeza obuzibu bwomunnyo ggwa zinc omutono mu baana butono nnyo. Abaana abatalina munnyo guno mubipimo ebimala balwalalwala nnyo era luusi nebafa endwadde ezisobolwa okuziyizibwa. Ebikwata ku munnyo

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IRB NO: 21107 19

ggwa zinc okubeera omutono mubaana abaweebwa ebitanda mu ddwaliro ekkulu e Masaka tebimanyiddwa. N'olwekyo, okunonyereza kun kugendereddwa okutumanyisa obungi bwabaana abaweebwa ebitanda mu ddwaliro ekkulu e Masaka nga tebalina munnyo gwa zinc gummala mumibiri ggyabwe. Ebinaava mukunonyereza bijja kuyamba ku basawo kumbuddabudda y'abaana abalwadde.

Ekigendererwa kyokunonyereza kuno:

Ekigendererwa kyokunonyereza kuno kwekwagala okumanya okubawo kwomunyo gwa zinc omubaana abaweebwa ebitanda muddwaliro ekkulu e Masaka, era n'okumanya akabi akava mumunyo ggwa zinc okuba omutono mumusaayi mukulwanisa endwadde. Okunonyereza kuno, kwakwejumbirwamu abaana anana abari wakati w'emyezi kumin'ebiri n'emyezi attaano mumwenda. Abaana abogeddwako waggulu bankizo olwensonga nti bakyakula naddala obwongo bwabwe. Ggwe n'omwana mujja mukwetaba mukunonyeraza kuno. Tujja kwetaaga eddakiika assatu zokka ng'omwana awereddwa ekitanda .

Lwaki osadiddwa okwetaba mu kunonyereza kuno?

Osabiddwa okwetaba mukunonyereza kuno ekisooka ggwe mujjanjabi w'omwana ono awereddwa ekitanda. Ekirala twetaaga okumanya ekipimo kyomunyo gwa zinc mumubiri gw'omwana kitusobozese okumanya ddala oba ekipimo ekyo kikwatagana nengeri omubiri gw'omwana gyegulwanisa endwadde.

Ebyokolebwa:

Bwonakiriza ggwe n'omwana okwetaba mukunonyereza, omusawo ajja kupima obuzito bw'omwana, okupima obuwanvu bwe, nobugaazi bwakitundu kyomukono wansi we kibegabega. Tujja mujjako omusaayi mutono, nga akajjiiko kamu akapima sukaali.. Omusaayi guno tujja ggweyambisa okumanya ekipimo kyomunyo ggwa zinc, wamu nebirala omubiri ggwebyetaaga mukulwanyisa endwadde okugeza nga ngowendo abaserikale b'omubiri. Omusaayi guno gujja kozesebwa munonyereza kuno kwokka.

Kabi ki akali mukunonyereza kuno?

Omwan ayinza okuggwako emirembe olwokumujjamo engoye akupima obuwanvu nobuzito bwe. Tujja kukola mu bwangu tukendeeze kubudde bwamala ngataymbadde. Era omwan ajjakulumizibwamu ngajjibwaako omusaayi. Abasawo abalina obukugu bebajja okujjako omwana omusaayi. Okuziyiza obutambuza ndwadde, tujjakozesa mpiso mpya etakozesebwangako okujjako omusaayi.

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MUST-REC Stamp:	
	REC OFFICE USE ONLY: APPROVAL DATE: <i>September 21, 2021</i> APPROVED CONSENT IRB VERSION NUMBER: <i>September 2021</i> PI NAME: <i>Muse Kanyeh</i> IRB NO: <i>24/07-19</i>

Amagoba

Abasawo baja kozesa ebinaava mu musaayi okuwa omwana obujjanjabi bweyetaaga ngabwamutindo. Singa omwan asangibwa ngalina obujjanjabi obwenjawulo bweyetaaga, tujja kutegeeza omusawo mbagirawo, era tuyambe nokubuwereza. Era ebinaava mukunonyereza kuno bijja kukuyamba abasawo okwongera kumutindo ogwokujjanjaba nokubudabuda abaanagwobuhereza ha'baana abaine omwonyo gwa zinc mukye omumubiri hamwe nokubakubasa kurwanisa endwara. Kukyakashangwa ngu omwana wawe nayetenga obujanjabi bwomutano, noyija kwanjurwa owomushaho orakuyambe kutunga okukwerwa okwo.

Empeera y'okwetaba mukunonyerezakuno:

Tetusasula kwetaba mukunonyereza kuno. Tujja kuwaayo omuti gwa sabuuni nekiro yasukaali emu mungeri yokwebazaamu okutuwa akadde n'okiriza okwetaba mukunonyereza

Okukuuma ebiwandiiko ebyokunonyereza mukyama

Tujja kukuuma ebiwandiiko byonna ebikwata kukunonyereza kuno mukyaama. Okutukuriza kino, tetujja kozesa manya ga mwana kiwandiiko kyonna. Tujja kozesa ennamba eyenjwulo emanyikiddwa banonyereza bokka. Foomu eno ekusaba olukusa lwokwetaba nomwana mukunonyereza kuno, yokka yejja okuwandikwako erinnya lyo nery'omwana. Ebiwandiiko bijja kumbwa mu ofiisi esibibwa n'ekuffulu era teri muntu mulala yenna akjja kukirizibwa kwata kubiwandiiko bino okujjako abo bokka abanonyoreza ngabakiriziddwa ne'ensonga. Akakiiko akalondola okunonyereza oluusi kandisaba olukusa okuyita mubiwandiiko bino okulambika obulambulukufu mukunonyereza. Bekinabaawo kino, tujja kakasa nti abo bokka bekikwatako bebefuna olukusa okulaba kubiwandiiko bino

Okukuuma ebyama ngatukunganya obubaka okuva eri abetabi mukunonyereza.

Twongera okikaturiza, nti amamyaga go nagomwana sigakozesebwa wantu walala okujjako kukiwandiko kino ekikusaba okwetaba mukunonyereza. Ebibuzo ebinakubuzibwa abanonyereza bijja kubuzibwa mukasenge akenjawulo akatekebwaawo era temujja kuba bantu balala. .

Eddembe lyokwamuka oba okugaana okwetaba mu kunonyereza

Oli waddembe okukiriza oba okugaana okwetaba mukunonyereza kuno. Era oli waddembe okwamuka okunonyereza kuno newankubadde oyinza okuba mukusooka wakkiriza okwetabamu. Ekibuuzo ekinakuzibuwalira okuddamu, otugamba netukibuuka.

Ki ekinabaawo singa n'abakunonyereza kuno?

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	APPROVED CONSENT IRB VERSION NUMBER: 2021
	PI NAME: NAME KENETH
	IRB NO: 21107-19

Ggwe n'omwaana muli baddembe okuva mukunonyereza kuno akasera konna woyagalidde. Ngera kino sikyateteganya kufuna bujjanjabi n'okubudabudibwa mungeri yonna nga muli muddwaliro. Teri kibonerezo kinaweebwa oyo yenna anayamuka okunonyereza kuno.

Ani ggwe nebuuzaako nganina ekibuuzo kukunonyereza kuno oba singa nfunu ekizibu?

Ojja tukirira abanonyereza bano wammanga
Dr. Keneth Male Essimu: 0788 394594, 0701 294594

Associate Professor Gertrude Kiwanuka. Essimu: 0772 350425.

Dr. Barnabas Atwiine Essimu: 0782 776660.

Oba ssentebe wekakiiko akalunganya n'okulondoola enbyokunonyereza ku ssetendekero lye Mbarara University of Science and Technology

Dr. Francis Bajunirwe,
Chairman MUST IRC,
Mbarara University of Science and Technology,
PO Box 1410, Mbarara,
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Okusa omukono ggwo oba ekinkumu ku foomu yokumanyisibw kitegeezaaki?

Okusa omukono ggwo ku foomu eno kitegeeza nti:

- Omanyisibwa ku bigendererwa by'okunonyereza kuno, ebinakolebwa, ebirungi ebinavaamu n'akabi konna akasobola okuva mukwetaba mukunonyereza kuno.
- Owereddwa omukisa gw'okubuuzo ebibuuzo nga tonasa mukono ku foomu eno
- Okiriza mubutali buwaze okwetaba mukunonyereza kuno.

Erinnya lyomuntu omukulu wano Ekinkumu/Omukono gw'omuntu omukulu Ennaku z'omwezi

Erinnya ly'oyo abuuza Omukono/ekinkumu gw'oyo abuuza Ennaku z'omwezi

Erinnya ly'omujulizi Ekinkumu/Omukono gw'omujulizi Ennaku z'omwezi

Leave blank for Office Only		REC OFFICE USE ONLY:
MUST-REC Stamp		APPROVAL DATE: <i>October 12, 2024</i>
		APPROVED CONSENT IRB VERSION NUMBER: <i>September 2024</i>
		PI NAME: <i>Keneth Male</i>
		IRB NO: <i>21107-19</i>

**Appendix 5: Clinical Record form 1 Participant Examination Findings
DATA COLLECTION FORM**

A. Is the child between 12-59 months?

Yes No

B. Has the child received **zinc** (as treatment for diarrhoea, in nutritional feeds for treatment of malnutrition, or flu) in the past 28 days?

Yes No

1. Child's demographics

Age in months/date of birth: _____

Sex: _____. Study No: _____

Inpatient No:- _____

2. Child's current illness

Date of admission: _____ Time of admission: _____

Diagnosis at admission: _____

Vital signs: Temp (°C): _____ Respiratory rate (bpm): _____ Heart rate (bpm): _____

3. General health status comments:

Distress: Yes No *Pallor:* Yes No

Jaundice: Yes No

Oedema: Yes No Bilateral Unilateral

Hydration status: Dry skin (poor skin turgor) Normal skin

4. Anthropometry

Weight (kg): _____. Height/Length (cm): _____. MUAC (cm): _____.

5. Stigmata of zinc deficiency (Tick appropriately):

Attribute	Yes	No
Hair: sparse, brown, easily pluckable		
Cheilitis, stomatitis: Wounds on the lips/inside mouth or on the tongue (<i>non-traumatic</i>)		
Stunting (Length/Height-for-age (<-3 SD))		

Z scores (tick appropriately):

SD	-3SD	-2SD	-1SD	MEDIAN	1SD	2SD	3SD
Weight-for-Height/Length							
Height/Length-for-Age							

Appendix 6. Assessment of serum zinc levels by flame atomic absorption spectrophotometry (FAAS)

Reagents: concentrated HCl 37% (Panreac Quimica, Spain), Concentrated HNO₃ 35.4% (LOBA Chemie, India) Ultra-pure de-ionised water 0.05µScm⁻¹(Popular laboratories, Uganda), zinc stock solution Spectran 1007µg/mL 2% (v/v) HNO₃ (Technolab, Sweden), pure glycerol >98% (VWR Int., Belgium), Certified Reference Material BCR®- 637 (Human serum zinc 1110 µg/L, EC-JRC-IRRM, Belgium).

Reagent, standard, sample and control preparation:

All equipment was acid-washed by soaking it in 0.1N HCl overnight and rinsed 5 times in ultra-pure water. Zinc stock solution was reconstituted into (Zn 2% HNO₃) into Zn 5% HNO₃ by adding 150 ml 10% HNO₃ to the 250 ml of Zn 2% HNO₃. A 5% HNO₃ is prepared as a sample and standard diluent.

Known concentrations of Zinc standards (0.0393, 0.3930, 0.7860, 1.5720 and 1.9650 mg/L) were prepared with glycerol added in a ratio of 1:120 to match serum viscosity. Blank was sample/standard diluent and glycerol added 1:120. To samples and standard controls was added sample diluent in a ratio of 1:30.

1. Collect 1mL of blood into a pyrogen-free, endotoxin-free and anticoagulant-free red top BD vacutainer tube.
2. Centrifuge the sample for 10 mins at 4000 revolutions per minute (RPM). Collect and store the supernatant at -70°C. The sample is brought to room temperature before analysis.
3. Prepare diluent for making diluted samples and standard solutions:
4. Prepare standard solutions of known zinc concentrations Add pure glycerol to each standard and blank in order to match the matrix of the serum used in reference serum and samples.
5. -Construct a 3-point standard linear regression curve of absorbance against concentration after analysis
6. Prepare serum samples and controls for analyses into an acid-washed trace-free tube Mix thoroughly on a vortex machine.
7. Allow standards, control and samples to be at room temperature before analyses.
8. Analyze blank (diluent) and standards first for calibration and to build the standard curve, followed by 2 reference serum samples.
9. Analyze 10 prepared serum samples. Recalibrate using the blank again and repeat the analytical sequence until all prepared samples have been analyzed.
10. Determine the concentration of the serum samples from the linear regression standard curve. Samples were measured using the atomic absorption spectrometer at 213.9 nm.

Instrumental arrangements used for analyses: wavelength 213.9 nm, instrument type; Flame, Slit width 1 nm, Mode: absorbance, Measurement time: 5 s, Lamp current: 5.0 mA, Burner height: 13.5 mm, Flame: Air/Acetylene, Airflow: 13.50L/min.

Equation for estimation of concentration (as provided by instrument)

$$Conc (ppm) = \frac{Abs}{-(-0.18940 * Abs^2 + 0.004973 * Abs + 0.27912)}$$

Standard curve

The standard working curve of zinc standards with confidence (95%) bands that show the likely location of the TRUE curve.

Values above 125 $\mu\text{g/dL}$ (after multiplying with dilution factors) were not considered for further analyses.

Appendix 7. ELISA for IL-2

Reagents. Human IL-2 standard solution, pre-coated ELISA 48- and 96-well plates, standard diluent, streptavidin-HRP, stop solution, substrate solutions A and B, wash buffer concentrate, biotinylated human IL-2 (hIL-2) antibody.

Specimen preparation. Collect 1mL of blood into a pyrogen-free, endotoxin-free and anticoagulant-free red top BD vacutainer tube. Allow serum to clot for 10-20 minutes at room temperature.

Reagent preparation. Bring all reagents to room temperature.

Standard preparation. Reconstitute 120 μL standard (2400ng/L) with standard diluent to generate standard stock solution (1200ng/L). Allow it to stand for 15 mins with gentle agitation. Prepare serial dilutions from the standard stock solutions as shown below.

concentration (ng/L)	standard no.	preparation
1200	No.5	120 μL original standard + 120 μL standard diluent
600	No.4	120 μL standard No.5 + 120 μL standard diluent
300	No.3	120 μL standard No. 4 + 120 μL standard diluent
150	No.2	120 μL standard No.3 + 120 μL standard diluent
75	No.1	120 μL standard No.2 + 120 μL standard diluent

Wash buffer. Dilute wash buffer concentrate (20mL) 25X into distilled water to yield 500mL. Mix gently till all crystals dissolve.

Assay procedure:

1. Prepare all reagents and samples as instructed above.
2. Prepare a worksheet for the tests and label strips according, that's locations for the controls, blank and serum samples in duplicates as they are to be. Use only required number of strips and seal the unused in provided pack and store at 2-8 $^{\circ}\text{C}$.
3. Add 50 μL standards to designated standard wells. Add 40 μL samples to sample wells and then 10 μL human anti-IL-2 antibody to sample wells, and no to standard wells

4. Add 50µL of streptavidin-HRP to standard and sample wells. Mix well. Cover the plates with a sealer and incubate at 37°C for 60 minutes.
5. Remove the seal and wash plate 5 times with wash buffer by soak wells with 350µL wash buffer for 30 seconds for each wash. Blot the plate carefully onto an absorbent paper.
6. Add 50µL substrate solution A followed by 50µL substrate solution B to each well. Seal and incubate the plate for 10 minutes at 37°C in the dark.
7. Add 50µL stop solution to all wells.
8. Read the absorbance (optical density, OD) of all wells with a microplate reader set to 450nm within 10 mins after adding the stop solution. Subtract the average OD of the blanks from all OD of standards and samples.
9. Construct a standard curve by plotting the average of the OD for each standard against the concentration of the standards. Use a computer-based curve-fitting statistical software, to draw a curve of best fit (smooth) and calculate the concentration of the sample using regression analysis.

Standard curve

IL-2 Standard Curve with Prediction bands (at 95% C.I.s)

The standard working curve of IL-2 standards with confidence (95%) bands that show the likely location of the TRUE curve.

Appendix 8. ELISA for IL-4

Reagents. Human IL-4 standard solutions, pre-coated ELISA 48- and 96-well plates, standard and sample diluents, biotinylated human IL-4 antibody and diluent, enzyme conjugate and diluent, colour reagents A, B and C, wash solution concentrate.

Specimen preparation. Collect 1mL of blood into a pyrogen-free, endotoxin-free and anticoagulant-free BD vacutainer Clot Activator tube. Allow serum to clot for 10-20 minutes at room temperature.

Reagent preparation. Bring all reagents to room temperature.

Standard preparation. Add 1mL of standard diluent into the human IL-4 lyophilized standard. Mix well. Allow it to stand for 30 min. Prepare serial dilutions from the standard stock solutions as shown below:

concentration (pg/mL)	standard no.	preparation
1000	No.1	dissolved original standard
500	No.2	300µL standard No.1 + 300µL standard diluent
250	No.3	300µL standard No.2 + 300µL standard diluent

125	No.4	300µL standard No.3 + 300µL standard diluent
62.5	No.5	300µL standard No.4 + 300µL standard diluent
31.5	No.6	300µL standard No.5 + 300µL standard diluent
15.6	No.7	300µL standard No.6 + 300µL standard diluent
0	No.8	300µL standard diluent

Wash buffer. Dissolve wash buffer solution into distilled water (1:25). Mix gently till all crystals dissolve.

Human IL-4 antibody preparation. Add antibody diluent to the antibody (1:100). Prepare it 30 min in advance.

Enzyme-conjugate preparation. Dilute the conjugate with enzyme diluent (1:100). Prepare it 30 min in advance.

Colour reagent preparation. Mix colour reagents A and B (1:9 respectively) 30 min in advance.

Assay procedure:

1. Prepare all reagents and samples as instructed above.
2. Prepare a worksheet for the tests and label strips according, that's locations for the controls, blank and serum samples in duplicates as they are to be. Use only required number of strips and seal the unused in provided pack and store at 2-8°C.
3. Add 100µL of standards and samples to corresponding wells, blank is filled with standard diluent. Seal plate and incubate at 37°C for 90 min.
4. Wash the plate 2 times. Add 100µL biotinylated human IL-4 antibody to each well. Seal the plate and incubate at 37°C for 60 min.
5. Wash the plate 3 times. Add 100µL enzyme-conjugate to each well. Seal plate and incubate at 37°C for 30 min. Blanks maybe ignored for steps 3-5.
6. Wash plate 5 times. Add 100µL colour reagent to each well, including the blanks. Incubate in the dark at 37°C for 30 minutes. Add 100µL colour reagent C to all wells. Mix well. Read the optical density (OD) of the wells within 10 minutes after adding reagent C.
7. Subtract the average OD of the blanks from all OD of standards and samples.
8. Construct a standard curve by plotting the average of the OD for each standard against the concentration of the standards. Use a computer-based curve-fitting statistical software, to draw a curve of best fit (smooth) and calculate the concentration of the sample using regression analysis.

Standard curve

IL-4 Standard Curve with 95% C.I Prediction bands

The standard working curve of IL-4 standards with confidence (95%) bands that show the likely location of the TRUE curve.

Appendix 10. Comparisons of medians; 90% reference ranges of Hematological indices of Ugandan children and international values and proportions for those with lower values.

Hematological parameters	Current study N= 40 5 th and 95 th range	Kironde study (N= 395) 5 th and 95 th range	International ranges 5 th and 95 th range (Mayo Clinic, 2016)	Proportion (%) Below Normal range or above* (Kironde et al., 2013)
Full blood count				
Red blood cell count, $X10^6/\mu L$	3.57–4.31	3.97–5.71	3.84–5.10	45
Hemoglobin, g/dL	8.5–10.6	9.9–14.0	10.2–14.3	55
Mean corpuscular volume, fL	72.5–82.6	62.0–83.0	71.3–89.5	7.5, 30*
Mean corpuscular hemoglobin, pg	22.9–26.3	19.8–29.1	-	7.5
White blood cell, $X10^3/\mu L$	9.12–13.8	5.9–14.3	4.4–13.5	10, 32.5*
Neutrophils, $X10^3/\mu L$	2.91–6.31	1.29–4.67	1.19–8.29	5, 40*
Lymphocytes $X10^3/\mu L$	3.31–4.84	3.16–9.31	1.13–8.09	30, 7.5*
Monocytes $X10^3/\mu L$	0.94–2.18	0.09–0.65	0.19–1.15	0, 77.5*
Eosinophils $X10^3/\mu L$	0.01–0.08	0.08–1.41	0.00–0.82	-
Basophils $X10^3/\mu L$	0.04–0.09	0.00–0.23	0.00–0.10	-

* Values above where considered in a few instances for MCV, WBC, neutrophils, lymphocytes and monocytes.

Appendix 11. Comparison of study participant's IL-2 and -4 levels and those from an international setting (Eastern Europe, Moldova)

	Current study	Sciuca and Neamtu, 2015	Normal children*
Mean cytokine IL-2	241 (±288.1)	37.56 (±2.76)	20.0-100.85
IL-4	94.09 (±23.5)	51.02 (±2.37)	6-24
Th1/Th2 ratio [#]	2.6	0.7	3.3-4.2

[#] Th1/Th2 calculated as mean IL-2/mean IL-4. * values from (Sciuca and Neamtu, 2015)

Appendix 12. Comparison of hematological and serum parameters between children with normal and low serum zinc levels.

Parameter	Mean ±SD		P value
	Normal sZn	Zn deficient	
White blood cell, $X10^3/\mu L$	15.62±9.752	10.3±5.3	0.11
Neutrophils, $X10^3/\mu L$	7.71±5.66	4.75±3.37	0.32
Lymphocytes $X10^3/\mu L$	5.67±3.96	3.85±2.14	0.15
Monocytes $X10^3/\mu L$	1.7±1.15	1.84±1.78	0.66
Eosinophils $X10^3/\mu L$	0.09±0.12	0.092±0.141	0.87
Basophils $X10^3/\mu L$	0.44±1.14	0.055±0.033	0.09
Serum Albumin, g/L	36.05±4.48	34.31±8.05	0.83
Serum cRP, mg/L*	46.78±2.74	54.2±2.64	0.60
IL-2, pg/mL*	170.2±3.06	138.0±1.98	0.22
IL-4, pg/mL ^a	95.72±27.29	92.74±20.75	0.74
Th1/Th2 ratio	3.87±5.54	2.02±2.01	0.42

* Geometric means, ^a student's t test otherwise Mann Whitney U tests performed.